

Probing the stacking properties of nucleosides and nucleotides with heteroaromatic amines and the effect of metal ion-bridging on the stability of the stacks. Implications for biological systems[†]

Nicolas A. Corfù, Astrid Sigel, Bert P. Operschall and Helmut Sigel*

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry, University of Basel, Spitalstrasse 51, CH-4056 Basel, Switzerland

E-mail : Helmut.Sigel@unibas.ch Fax : ++41-61-2671017

Manuscript received 24 May 2011, accepted 25 May 2011

Abstract : Noncovalent interactions play important roles in modern chemical research encompassing also bio-systems. Among these interactions aromatic-ring stacking is especially pronounced as, next to hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic and ionic interactions, it is crucial for the three-dimensional structure of nucleic acids (RNA, DNA) and proteins (enzymes). We have now measured by ¹H-NMR shift experiments the stability of binary stacks formed between purine nucleosides or nucleotides (N) and the "indicator" ligand 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), and we also reviewed the related literature. Surprisingly, we observe that the stability of the (Phen)(N) adducts is largely independent of the type of purine residue involved, including deprotonation, e.g., at (N1)H of a guanine moiety, and also of the location of the phosphate group at the ribosyl ring. This contrasts with the self-stacking tendency which decreases within the series adenosine > guanosine > inosine > cytidine ~ uridine. Interestingly, the formation of an ionic (+/-) or metal ion (M²⁺) bridge stabilizes the formation of stacks as observed, e.g., in mixed ligand Cu²⁺ complexes formed between Phen and adenosine 5'-monophosphate (5'-AMP²⁻); yet, in these instances the position of the phosphate group at the ribosyl ring affects the stability of the stacks: It decreases in the order 2'-AMP²⁻ > 5'-AMP²⁻ > 3'-AMP²⁻ in the Cu(Phen)(AMP) complexes demonstrating a significant steric discrimination. The stability of stacks also depends on the size of the aromatic-ring systems involved; as one would expect, purines stack better than pyrimidines and Phen generally better than 2,2'-bipyridine. Results obtained with various mixed ligand metal ion complexes containing adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP⁴⁻) and an amino acid anion (Aa⁻) lead to the conclusion: The recognition of the adenine residue by the amino acid side chain in M(ATP)(Aa)³⁻ complexes decreases in the series tryptophan (indole residue) > histidine (imidazole residue) > leucine (isopropyl residue) > alanine (methyl group). This type of selectivity is certainly of relevance for amino acid/protein interactions with nucleotides/nucleic acids. The addition of an organic solvent like 1,4-dioxane reduces the solvent polarity and decreases the stability of binary stacks like (Phen)(ATP)⁴⁻ dramatically; in contrast, intramolecular stacks, as present in Cu(Phen)(ATP)²⁻, are much less affected. Because the "effective" dielectric constant or permittivity in the active site cavity of an enzyme or a ribozyme is lower than in bulk water, Nature has here a further tool to achieve selectivity. Here it needs to be noted that the involved changes in free energy (ΔG^0) are small; e.g., a formation degree of 20% of an intramolecular stack in a mixed ligand complex corresponds only to about -0.6 kJ mol⁻¹ allowing Nature to shift such equilibria easily.

Keywords : Amino acids, aromatic-ring stacking, binary stacking adducts, intramolecular stacks, metal ion complexes, nucleic acids, 1,10-phenanthroline, stability constants.

1. Introduction and overview

Noncovalent interactions play important roles in modern chemical research¹⁻⁴; they are considered as cornerstones in supramolecular chemistry⁵⁻⁷, materials science⁶⁻⁸ and bio-systems⁹⁻¹⁴ as well. Next to ionic attractions^{4,15-17},

hydrophobic interactions^{1,3,6,9,18-21} and hydrogen bonds²²⁻²⁶, π - π stacks^{10,17,22,27-30} are most often observed and their roles for the structures of DNA^{31,32} and RNA³³⁻³⁵ are well appreciated. Of course, π - π stacking also occurs in proteins, e.g., between the indole side chain

[†]This study is dedicated to Sir Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, to commemorate his 150th Birth Anniversary, in admiration and with great respect for all his unselfish achievements as Chemist, Educator and Philanthropist.

of tryptophan and the imidazole residue of histidine³⁶. Not surprisingly, stacking is important for charge transfer in proteins^{12,13,37} and also in the double helix of DNA³⁸. Indeed, it appears that the intensity of the various stacks within DNA affects the charge transport^{39,40}; self-stacking of the various nucleobase residues decreases in the order adenine > guanine > hypoxanthine > cytosine ~ uracil⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ (the value for thymine is expected to be at the lower end).

However, there are also more subtle interactions, which are generally less recognized though they can be very important. For example, in the Cu center of plastocyanin from the fern *Dryopteris crassirhizoma*⁴⁵, a phenylalanine residue is stacked with a coordinated histidine: This phenyl-imidazole π - π stack is probably responsible for the higher redox potential of this plastocyanin compared to those of higher plants. Related examples are the interactions of the antibiotics ciprofloxacin⁴⁶ and netropsin⁴⁷ with DNA, where, e.g., a methyl pyrrole ring of netropsin stacks with a guanine residue of the DNA⁴⁷.

Stacking interactions are also crucial for the metal ion-promoted hydrolysis of purine-nucleoside 5'-triphosphates^{28,48}: adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP²⁻) and its antivirally active⁴⁹ acyclic nucleotide analogue 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine (PMEA²⁻) facilitate further via stacking the Cu²⁺-promoted dephosphorylation of adenosine 5'-triphosphate⁵⁰. Stacking interactions also occur in 1,10-phenanthroline- or 2,2'-bipyridine-containing polyamine ATP-receptors⁵¹⁻⁵³ and these also promote the hydrolysis of ATP in the presence of divalent metal ions^{52,53}.

In fact, 2,2'-bipyridine (Bpy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) as well as derivatives thereof have proven very helpful as indicators for evaluating the stacking capabilities of aromatic residues in metal ion complexes¹⁰ of amino acids^{17,29,54} and nucleotides^{10,17,55-57}. Next to Pt²⁺ (cf. ^{10,17}), mostly Cu²⁺ (cf. ^{10,55-57}), but also other metal ions have been employed in these studies: For example, the M(Phen)₂(L)²⁺ complexes of Ni²⁺ and Ru²⁺, where L = Phen or a Phen derivative, were used to probe the effect of different metal ions (M²⁺) on the intercalating properties of these complexes into the DNA base stacks⁵⁸.

Thanks to the nucleotide units which occur in DNA

and RNA as well as to the general importance of nucleotides in bio-systems, the self-stacking properties of nucleosides^{41,43} as well as of their mono-^{59,60}, di-⁴² and triphosphates^{41,43,44,61} (see Fig. 1)^{31,59,62-64} have been studied in great detail^{10,65-68} including several derivatives like tubercidin (= 7-deazaadenosine)⁶⁹ and its 5'-monophosphate⁵⁹, or 1,N⁶-ethenoadenosine (ϵ -Ado) together with its phosphates^{70,71} as well as flavin mononucleotide (FMN²⁻)⁷². However, there is no comprehensive study on "hetero"-stacks. Therefore, we considered now stack formation of the common purine-nucleosides and their 5'-monophosphates (Fig. 1) by using Phen as the second, i.e., "indicator", ligand⁷³ allowing comparisons and conclusions about the stability of binary stacks in dependence on the structure of the purine residue.

Hence, we measured by ¹H-NMR shift experiments (see Section 3) the stability of the stack formed between a nucleobase derivative (N) and a heteroaromatic nitrogen base (Arm), in the present case 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), as defined by eq. (1) (possible charges of N are neglected):

$$K_{(\text{Arm})(\text{N})}^{(\text{N})} = [(\text{Arm})(\text{N})]/([\text{Arm}][\text{N}]) \quad (1b)$$

These results are compared with stability data available in the literature for other binary stacks which contain next to the nucleobase derivative another heterocycle like 2,2'-bipyridine (Bpy)⁷⁴⁻⁷⁷ or the indole⁷⁸⁻⁸¹ residue (Fig. 2); indeed, the aromatic amino-acid residues of tryptophan, phenylalanine and tyrosine⁸² as well as of histidine⁸³ are well-known for their stacking properties. Of course, the stability of such binary adducts is always defined in analogy to eq. (1).

Next, it is interesting to screen the literature for M(Arm)(N) systems (charge of N neglected) focusing on Arm = Phen, for which the extent of intramolecular stack (st) formation has been determined, that is, for equilibrium (2a),

$$K_{\text{I/st}} = [\text{M}(\text{Arm})(\text{N})_{\text{st}}]/[\text{M}(\text{Arm})(\text{N})_{\text{op}}] \quad (2b)$$

where M(Arm)(N)_{op} represents the open (op) and

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of the nucleobases (R = H: adenine, guanine, hypoxanthine, cytosine and uracil) of the nucleosides (Ns): adenosine (Ado), guanosine (Guo), inosine (Ino), cytidine (Cyd) and uridine (Urd). The respective 5'-nucleotides carry a phosphate residue at the 5' end of the ribose moiety: nucleoside 5'-monophosphate (NMP²⁻), i.e., adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP²⁻), guanosine 5'-monophosphate (GMP²⁻), etc.; nucleoside 5'-diphosphate (NDP³⁻), i.e., adenosine 5'-diphosphate (ADP³⁻), etc.; nucleoside 5'-triphosphate (NTP⁴⁻), i.e., adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP⁴⁻), etc. At the top of the figure are shown, as examples, adenosine 5'-triphosphate (5'-ATP⁴⁻) and cytidine 5'-triphosphate (5'-CTP⁴⁻) in their dominating *anti* conformation^{31,59,62-64}, together with the labeling system of the triphosphate chain; note, the phosphate groups in the NTPs are labeled α , β , and γ , where γ refers to the terminal phosphate group. The analogous NMPs and NDPs have the corresponding structures with one or two phosphate groups, respectively; the terminal phosphate group in the NDPs is labeled as β . The adenine and cytosine residues in the structures given at the top for 5'-ATP⁴⁻ and 5'-CTP⁴⁻, respectively, may be replaced by one of the other nucleobase residues shown above; if this substitution is done in the way the bases are depicted within the plane, then the *anti* conformation will also result for the corresponding nucleoside 5'-phosphates. The abbreviations AMP²⁻, ADP³⁻, ATP⁴⁻, GMP²⁻, etc. represent in this text always the 5'-derivatives; 2'- and 3'-derivatives are always defined by 2'-AMP²⁻, 3'-AMP²⁻, etc.; in a few instances, where otherwise uncertainties might occur, the abbreviations 5'-AMP²⁻, 5'-ADP³⁻, etc. are also used. The self-association constants for the above nucleosides and their phosphate derivatives are found in the literature^{10,41-43}.

M(Arm)(N)_{st} the stacked (st) isomer. The intramolecular equilibrium (2a) is depicted in a simplified manner for a nucleoside 5'-monophosphate in equilibrium (3):

We concentrate in this account on Cu²⁺ complexes for three reasons: (i) Many comparisons are possible for

this metal ion, as indicated above; (ii) the stability of the Cu(Phen)²⁺ complex is high^{84,85}, which facilitates comparisons; and (iii) Cu²⁺ is itself a biologically important metal ion^{86,87} which participates in crucial metabolic processes^{88,89}. However, where appropriate, other metal ions (and ligand combinations) are considered as well, if data were available.

Consequently, in this article original experimental data (see Sections 3 and 9) are presented and at the same time the connected literature is reviewed. Maybe already at this point a caveat should be emphasized, namely that a

Fig. 2. Chemical structures of the heteroaromatic nitrogen bases (Arm) considered in this study, i.e., of 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) and 2,2'-bipyridine (Bpy), as well as of two amino acids which also allow adduct formation due to their side chains: tryptophan (Trp[±]) and leucine (Leu[±]).

direct comparison of the equilibrium constants defined in eqs. (1b) and (2b) is not possible because these K values carry different dimensions (M^{-1} versus dimensionless).

2. Some comments on the self-association of nucleobase derivatives

Considering the indicated situation in the double helix of DNA and the involved nucleobase stacking³¹, it is not surprising that the self-association of purines and pyrimidines as well as of their nucleosides has long been recognized. Already nearly 50 years ago it was shown that purines associate much better than pyrimidines⁹⁰. Regarding nucleotides the situation was less clear for many years⁹¹. Today it is generally accepted that self-association of all these species occurs via base stacking⁹¹⁻⁹³, that it proceeds beyond the dimer stage and that oligomers are formed^{41,42,91,93,94}. As far as purines, especially adenine derivatives, are concerned, "head-to-tail" stacking with the five-membered and six-membered rings alternating in the stack, has been suggested⁹⁵, but other

geometries are also possible^{43,44,92,93,96}.

Most often ¹H-NMR shift measurements have been applied to characterize the self-association of nucleosides and nucleotides (= N) in aqueous solution (D₂O)^{41,42,65,91}. These measurements confirm due to the observed upfield shifts with increasing concentration that the association occurs via stacking of the aromatic moieties. In most instances the experimental data can be explained best by application of the isodesmic model for an indefinite non-cooperative self-association^{41,43,91}; i.e., all association constants, K_{SA} , are considered as equal^{91,93,97}:

$$K_{SA} = [(N)_{n+1}] / [(N)_n][N] \quad (4b)$$

Of course, more complicated models (with more variables) can also be applied⁹⁸.

Based on eq. (4) one obtains the following order for a decreasing self-stacking tendency for the nucleosides (the K_{SA} values according to eq. (4b), with twice the standard error (2σ), are given in parentheses)⁴¹: Ado ($15 \pm 3 M^{-1}$) > Guo (8 ± 3) > Ino (3.3 ± 0.3) > Cyd (1.4 ± 0.5) \approx Urd (1.2 ± 0.5) (see also Fig. 1). The order for the nucleoside 5'-triphosphates is analogous but the size of the values is much smaller due to charge repulsion of the triphosphate chains⁴¹: ATP⁴⁻ ($1.3 \pm 0.2 M^{-1}$) > GTP⁴⁻ (0.8 ± 0.6) > ITP⁴⁻ (0.4 ± 0.3) \sim CTP⁴⁻ (0.5 ± 0.2) \sim UTP⁴⁻ (ca. 0.4). The position of the phosphate group at the ribose residue does not significantly affect self-stacking as the following series shows⁵⁹: 2'-AMP²⁻ ($2.0 \pm 0.2 M^{-1}$) \sim 3'-AMP²⁻ (1.6 ± 0.4) \sim 5'-AMP²⁻ (2.1 ± 0.3) \sim 7-deaza-5'-AMP²⁻ (= TuMP²⁻: 2.1 ± 0.3); hence, replacement of N7 (see Fig. 1) by CH has also no remarkable effect.

However, protonation can lead to surprises: For H₂(ATP)²⁻, which carries a proton at N1 and at the terminal γ -phosphate group, at pH ca. 3 the self-stacking tendency increases tremendously leading to a K_{SA} value of about 200 M⁻¹ with a dimeric species, [H₂(ATP)]₂⁴⁻, dominating^{43,99}. The reason is that the dimeric stack is stabilized by intramolecular hydrogen bridges. Similarly, metal ion coordination facilitates stacking of nucleotides due to charge neutralization of the phosphate groups, but also due to bridging by binding to N7 next to the phosphate residue (Zn²⁺)^{41,42,71}.

In studies aiming for the properties of monomeric

nucleoside or nucleotide species, including metal ion complexes, it is recommended to work with 10^{-3} M (or more diluted) solutions^{41,42,65,66}. Calculations based on $K_{SA} = 15 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for Ado, which is the highest value in the above series, show that in a 10^{-3} M solution 97% of Ado is present in its monomeric form. Indeed, any results from metal ion-containing solutions which will be discussed in Sections 6 and 7 were obtained from solutions with $[N] < 1 \text{ mM}$ and thus they refer to the properties of monomers. In the experiments regarding the binary (Phen)(N) adducts (eq. (1)) the situation is somewhat more complicated as will be discussed in the next section.

3. Stabilities of binary (Phen)(N) stacks formed between the "indicator" ligand 1,10-phenanthroline and nucleosides or nucleotides

3.1. Evaluations aiming for the optimal experimental conditions

The stability of binary (Phen)(N) stacks, e.g., (Phen)(AMP)²⁻, is not very high¹⁰⁰ and therefore it is necessary to employ in the experiments relatively large concentrations of N to achieve a reasonable formation degree of the stacks allowing to measure the stability constant (eq. (1)). Satisfying results were obtained with $[N] = 5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Yet with this procedure self-association of N cannot be completely ignored. To mediate a feeling for the situation Table 1 has been prepared.

Table 1. Percentages of the monomers, dimers, etc., that occur in a 5 mM aqueous solution (D₂O) of N in dependence on the size of the self-association constant, $K_{SA} \text{ M}^{-1}$, as defined in eq. (4)

Species	n in eq. (4)	% calculated with $K_{SA} =$			
		15 M^{-1}	8 M^{-1}	4 M^{-1}	2 M^{-1}
monomer	0	87.33	92.72	96.19	98.05
dimer	1	11.44	6.88	3.70	1.92
trimer	2	1.12	0.38	0.11	0.03
tetramer	3	0.10	0.02	-	-

From the data in Table 1 it is evident that with $K_{SA} = 15 \text{ M}^{-1}$, which is the self-association constant for adenosine^{41,91} and $[N] = 5 \text{ mM}$ according to the isodesmic model (eq. (4); Section 2), only about 87% of the analytical concentration of Ado present exist in the monomeric form and that about 11% are (Ado)₂ dimers. For all the other systems the self-stacking tendency of N is not really

a problem: For example, for $K_{SA} = 8 \text{ M}^{-1}$, which corresponds to the constant for Guo⁴¹, already nearly 93% of the total Guo occur as monomers, the dimers (Guo)₂ being below 7%. For a self-association constant of $K_{SA} = 4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (which is close to $K_{SA/Ino}$)⁴¹ more than 96% of N occur as monomers. Finally, with $K_{SA} = 2 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (or even lower), which is valid for most other N systems considered, the concentration of monomeric N encompasses more than 98% and any associated species are thus clearly negligible. To conclude, the situation for Ado is not ideal but the results of the experiments show that they are still reasonable, even in this case.

Because it was the aim of this study to investigate well defined species, the acid-base properties^{101,102} of the nucleosides (Ns) and their 5'-monophosphates (NMP²⁻) (Fig. 1) had to be taken into account as well (see also Ref. 103). For example, Ado accepts a proton at N1, whereas Ino and Guo do so at N7; hence, for all three nucleosides eq. (5) applies;

$$K_{\text{H(N)}}^{\text{H}} = [\text{N}][\text{H}^+]/[\text{H(N)}^+] \quad (5b)$$

However, Ino and Guo may at higher pH values also lose a proton from their (N1)H site and then reaction (6) occurs;

$$K_{\text{N}}^{\text{H}} = [(\text{N} - \text{H})^-][\text{H}^+]/[\text{N}] \quad (6b)$$

The expression (N - H)⁻ is to be read as "nucleobase moiety minus a proton". The acidity constants for H₂(NMP)[±] species, where one proton is at the nucleobase residue and one at the phosphate group, are defined accordingly.

The acidity constants for the various nucleobase derivatives are known for aqueous solutions at 25°C and $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ ^{101,102}. These values are assembled in the left-hand part (columns 2-4) of Table 2. Since the ¹H-NMR shift experiments were carried out in D₂O, the acidity constants need to be transformed to this solvent¹⁰⁴ with eq. (7):

$$pK_{a/D_2O} = 1.015 \cdot pK_{a/H_2O} + 0.45 \quad (7)$$

The corresponding results are given in the right-hand part of Table 2. Similarly, for H(Phen)⁺ it holds in aqueous solution $pK_{\text{H(Phen)}}^{\text{H}} = 4.98$ (25°C; $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$, KCl)⁸⁴ [in excellent accord with 4.95 (20°C; $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$, NaNO₃)]⁸⁵ which gives with eq. (7) for D₂O as solvent $pK_{\text{D(Phen)}}^{\text{D}} = 5.50$ [5.47].

Table 2. Negative logarithms of the acidity constants (pK_a) of some protonated purine-nucleosides and their 5'-monophosphates (eqs. (5) and (6)) as determined by potentiometric pH titrations in aqueous solution at 25°C and $I = 0.1$ M (NaNO_3). The values valid for D_2O as solvent were calculated with eq. (7)^{a,b}

H(N)	pK_a in H_2O			pK_a in D_2O		
	(N1)H ⁺ /(N7)H ⁺	P(O) ₂ (OH) ⁻	(N1)H	(N1)D ⁺ /(N7)D ⁺	P(O) ₂ (OD) ⁻	(N1)D
H(Ado) ⁺	3.61 ± 0.03 ^c			4.11		
H(Ino) ⁺	1.06 ± 0.06 ^d		8.76 ± 0.03	1.53		9.34
H(Guo) ⁺	2.11 ± 0.04 ^d		9.22 ± 0.01	2.59		9.81
H ₂ (AMP) [±]	3.84 ± 0.02 ^c	6.21 ± 0.01		4.35	6.75	
H ₂ (IMP) [±]	1.30 ± 0.10 ^e	6.22 ± 0.01	9.02 ± 0.02	1.77	6.76	9.61
H ₂ (GMP) [±]	2.48 ± 0.04 ^d	6.25 ± 0.02	9.49 ± 0.02	2.97	6.79	10.08

^a The errors given are three times the standard error of the mean value or the sum of the probable systematic errors, whichever is larger.

^b The values for Ado and AMP are from Ref. 101, all the others are from Ref. 102.

^c The proton is at N1 (see Fig. 1).

^d The proton is at N7 (see Fig. 1).

^e The proton is mainly at N7; see Fig. 2 in Ref. 102 for the micro acidity constant.

The pD values to be adjusted in the experiments (see Section 9.2) were derived by the following reasonings: For example, with regard to Phen/Ino this pD for the experiments needs to be selected which is between the acidity constants $pK_{\text{D(Phen)}}^{\text{D}} = 5.47$ and $pK_{\text{Ino}}^{\text{D}} = 9.34$, that is, pD = 7.41; in other words, at a pD close to 7.4 Phen is overwhelmingly unprotonated and Ino has not yet lost the proton from its (N1)H site and thus, the adduct formation occurs between the two neutral, uncharged species, giving the (Phen)(Ino) stack. For the (Phen/IMP)²⁻ system the desired pD has to be close to 8.2, which is between $pK_{\text{D(IMP)}}^{\text{D}} = 6.76$ and $pK_{\text{IMP}}^{\text{H}} = 9.61$, and for Phen/Ado, Phen/AMP²⁻ and related systems a pD value of about 1.5 pK units above the relevant pK_a was adjusted (see column 3 in Table 3, *vide infra*) (see also Section 9.2).

3.2. Determination of the stability of binary (Phen)(N) stacks by ¹H-NMR

As adduct formation according to eq. (1) occurs via aromatic-ring stacking, it should be possible to determine the stability of such adducts by ¹H-NMR shift measurements; indeed, from earlier studies^{100,105} of the Phen/AMP²⁻ and Phen/ATP⁴⁻ systems the experimental procedure is already well developed. Therefore, the stability constants for the (Phen)(N) stacks were determined in 5 mM solutions of N in D_2O by adding increasing amounts of Phen until a Phen concentration of approximately 0.018 M was reached (which is close to the solubility limit).

The chemical shifts in ppm of the resonances of H2 (if available), H8, and H1' of the purine residues (see Fig. 1) were measured as a function of the analytical concentration of Phen. In this way the equilibrium constant $K_{\text{(Phen)(N)}}^{(\text{N})}$ (eq. (1)), was determined via a curve-fitting procedure¹⁰⁵. A typical example is shown in Fig. 3 (see also Section 9).

Under the experimental conditions some self-association of Phen occurs, that is, the analytical concentration of Phen does not correspond to the active free concentration because due to the self-association of Phen a part of the aromatic rings is no longer available for a stacking interaction with the purine moiety of the nucleobase derivatives. This difficulty may be accounted for by replacing the analytical concentration by the active particle concentration, $\Sigma_n[(\text{Phen})_n]$, which can be calculated with the known constant for the self-association of Phen, i.e., $K_{\text{SA}} = 31.1 (\pm 3.4/2\sigma)^{105}$. The results are graphs similar to the one shown in Fig. 3. This procedure leads to corrected stability constants, $K_{\text{(Phen)(N)cor}}^{(\text{N})}$. These values are larger by factors of ca. 1.3–1.4 (see Table 3) compared with those calculated neglecting the self-association of Phen^{100,105}.

As indicated in Fig. 3, the chemical shift of each proton, H2, H8, and H1' is individually evaluated meaning that from the increasing upfield shifts obtained for each proton an association constant K according to eq. (1) was calculated. These individual values are listed in column 8 of Table 3 and their average for a given (Phen)(N) adduct

Fig. 3. Variation of the chemical shift, δ , of H8, H2 and H1' of inosine ($5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M) with increasing concentrations of 1,10-phenanthroline in D_2O solutions at pD 7.44 ($25^\circ C$, $I = 0.1$ M, $NaNO_3$). The spectra were measured at a Varian VXR400 spectrometer at 399.96 MHz, relative to internal $(CH_3)_4N^+/NO_3^-$ and converted to values relative to sodium 3-(trimethylsilyl)propane-1-sulfonate by adding 3.174 ppm¹⁰⁵. The curves shown are the computer-calculated best fits of the experimental data in the [Phen] range of 0 to 0.019 M, calculated with $K_{av} = K_{(Phen)(Ino)}^{(Ino)} = 36.2$ M⁻¹ of Table 3 (eq. (1)); the resulting shifts are listed in Table 3 (see also Sections 3 and 9).

leads to the final result for $K_{(Phen)(N)}^{(N)}$ listed in column 9. The results obtained for the 10 Phen/N systems considered are summarized in Table 3 and one may add that the chemical shifts (ppm) measured now for free Ado agree well with previous data^{59,60}. The results of Table 3 allow many comparisons; a few follow below:

(i) For all Phen/N systems significant upfield shifts ($\Delta\delta_N$) are observed for the purine protons (see Fig. 1) H2 (where available), H8 and H1' confirming that the association occurs via aromatic-ring stacking between the purine system and the rings of Phen.

(ii) The shift differences ($\Delta\delta_N$) are quite similar for a given Phen/Ns and its corresponding Phen/NMP²⁻ system (cf., e.g., entries 1 and 4) when the error limits are taken into account. Evidently, deprotonation of the (N1)H site reduces the shift differences $\Delta\delta_N$ somewhat if compared with the undeprotonated species, e.g., (Phen)(Ino - H)⁻ with (Phen)(Ino) (entries 2 and 7).

(iii) However, the most unexpected result, at least for us, is the observation that the stability of the (Phen)(Ns) and (Phen)(NMP)²⁻ systems is independent of the deprotonation degree of the (N1)H site, that is, introducing a negative charge at the hypoxanthine or guanine residues (see Fig. 1) does not significantly affect the stability of the (Phen)(N) adducts.

(iv) Furthermore, most remarkable is the fact that the stacking tendency of all nucleobase residues, be it in Ns or NMP²⁻, towards Phen is very similar, i.e., the differences in charge have no effect. In fact, the average value obtained for the stability of the 10 (Phen)(N) adducts amounts to $K_{(Phen)(N)av}^{(N)} = 32.9 \pm 2.5$ M⁻¹ (2σ) and this value is within the error limits identical with the individual stability constants according to eq. (1) (cf. the data in column 9 of Table 3).

(v) Not surprisingly, the same applies, if the values corrected for the self-association of Phen are compared; the average $K_{(Phen)(N)cor/av}^{(N)} = 44.4 \pm 3.8$ M⁻¹ (2σ) overlaps within the error limits with the results listed in column 10 of Table 3. This value is by a factor of 1.35 larger than $K_{(Phen)(N)av}^{(N)} = 32.9$ M⁻¹.

To conclude, the result that the stability of the individual (Phen)(N) adducts, e.g. of (Phen)(Ado) and (Phen)(Ino), does hardly differ and that all the nucleobase residues have about the same affinity for the aromatic rings of Phen is very surprising and not expected. In contrast, the self-stacking tendency of these nucleobases differs significantly (see Section 2).

4. Stability comparisons between (Phen)(N) and related binary stacks

The most relevant result of Section 3 is the observation that all purine derivatives considered (Table 3) have the same affinity toward Phen. This led us to compile related stability data from the literature; these constants, also defined according to eq. (1), are listed¹⁰⁶ in Table 4.

Table 3. Chemical shifts in ppm of H2, H8, and H1' (Figs. 1 and 3) of free purine-nucleosides and nucleotides (N) and of these nucleobase derivatives with 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), together with the corresponding upfield shifts ($\Delta\delta_N = \delta_N - \delta_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})}$) resulting from the (Phen)(N) adduct formation, and the stability constants, K (M^{-1}), calculated for the individual protons, resulting in the average stability constant, $K_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})}^{(\text{N})}$ (M^{-1}), for the binary stacking adducts (eq. (1)) in D_2O at the pD given in column 3 (25°C; $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$, NaNO_3). The stability constants, $K_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})\text{cor}}^{(\text{N})}$ (M^{-1}), corrected for the self-association of Phen are also given (see text)^{a,b}

No.	(Phen)(N)	pD	H _N	δ_N	$\delta_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})}$	$\Delta\delta_N$	K	$K_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})}^{(\text{N})}$	$K_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})\text{cor}}^{(\text{N})}$
1	(Phen)(Ado)	7.53	H2	8.223 ± 0.013	7.22 ± 0.23	1.00 ± 0.23	30.73 ± 7.52	31.0 ± 9.5	42
			H8	8.314 ± 0.009	7.56 ± 0.17	0.75 ± 0.17	30.81 ± 7.30		
			H1'	6.055 ± 0.007	5.49 ± 0.13	0.57 ± 0.13	31.32 ± 7.35		
2	(Phen)(Ino)	7.44	H2	8.215 ± 0.004	7.54 ± 0.05	0.68 ± 0.05	36.95 ± 3.25	36.2 ± 3.6	49
			H8	8.328 ± 0.002	7.92 ± 0.03	0.41 ± 0.03	34.63 ± 3.04		
			H1'	6.087 ± 0.002	5.66 ± 0.03	0.43 ± 0.03	37.04 ± 3.24		
3	(Phen)(Guo)	7.63	H8	7.981 ± 0.010	7.40 ± 0.15	0.58 ± 0.15	30.79 ± 7.15	31.0 ± 5.1	42
			H1'	5.896 ± 0.009	5.35 ± 0.14	0.55 ± 0.14	31.24 ± 7.14		
4	(Phen)(AMP) ²⁻	8.8	H2	8.246 ± 0.003	7.50 ± 0.10	0.75 ± 0.10	28.3 ± 5.4	29.7 ± 5.4	38
			H8	8.603 ± 0.002	8.20 ± 0.06	0.40 ± 0.06	27.8 ± 5.8		
			H1'	6.128 ± 0.002	5.72 ± 0.05	0.41 ± 0.05	30.9 ± 3.7		
5	(Phen)(IMP) ²⁻	8.20	H2	8.211 ± 0.002	7.70 ± 0.04	0.51 ± 0.04	36.92 ± 2.56	36.8 ± 4.5	49
			H8	8.571 ± 0.001	8.35 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.02	34.20 ± 2.64		
			H1'	6.135 ± 0.001	5.82 ± 0.03	0.32 ± 0.03	38.66 ± 2.54		
6	(Phen)(GMP) ²⁻	8.39	H8	8.199 ± 0.003	7.88 ± 0.07	0.32 ± 0.07	28.46 ± 5.36	27.6 ± 8.2	36
			H1'	5.924 ± 0.004	5.53 ± 0.09	0.39 ± 0.09	26.15 ± 6.30		
7	(Phen)(Ino - H) ⁻	11.15	H2	8.132 ± 0.003	7.82 ± 0.05	0.31 ± 0.05	48.51 ± 8.87	37.7 ± 8.3	51
			H8	8.135 ± 0.002	7.87 ± 0.04	0.27 ± 0.04	34.12 ± 5.37		
			H1'	6.010 ± 0.002	5.75 ± 0.04	0.26 ± 0.04	34.36 ± 5.51		
8	(Phen)(Guo - H) ⁻	11.27	H8	7.846 ± 0.002	7.57 ± 0.04	0.28 ± 0.04	32.90 ± 3.65	30.3 ± 5.3	42
			H1'	5.868 ± 0.002	5.60 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.03	27.59 ± 3.30		
9	(Phen)(IMP - H) ³⁻	11.26	H2	8.147 ± 0.001	7.90 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03	29.76 ± 2.62	30.3 ± 5.6	41
			H8	8.413 ± 0.001	8.27 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.02	28.53 ± 4.73		
			H1'	6.079 ± 0.001	5.88 ± 0.03	0.20 ± 0.03	31.92 ± 3.27		
10	(Phen)(GMP - H) ³⁻	11.29	H8	8.118 ± 0.001	8.03 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.02	39.13 ± 7.81	38.1 ± 10.0	54
			H1'	5.923 ± 0.001	5.80 ± 0.02	0.12 ± 0.02	37.29 ± 6.49		

^a The chemical shifts (ppm) were measured relative to internal $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+/\text{NO}_3^-$ and converted to values downfield from sodium 3-(trimethylsilyl)propane-1-sulfonate by adding 3.174 ppm (Fig. 3)¹⁰⁵. The listed limiting shifts were calculated with $K_{(\text{Phen})(\text{N})}^{(\text{N})}$, which is the weighted mean (calculated by using $\log K$) of the individual results. The range of error given with the values for K of the individual protons is the standard deviation (1σ); all other error limits correspond to twice the standard deviation (2σ). For the selection of the pD values and for further details see Sections 3 and 9.2. The values for the binary (Phen)(AMP)²⁻ adduct are taken from Table 1 of Ref. 100.

^b For entries 7–10 it should be noted that, e.g., (Ino - H)⁻, means that the (N1)H site (see Fig. 1) has lost its proton and it is therefore to be read as "inosine *minus* a proton". The various other expressions are written in the same analogous and conventional manner, even though in D_2O as solvent, of course, actually a deuterium cation is released from (N1)D⁺.

^c The error limits of these values are practically the same as those given in the column at the left.

The information assembled in Table 4 allows many conclusions; the most important ones follow below:

(i) Already in Section 3 (point (iv)) we have seen that the stability of the (Phen)(N) adducts for N = Ado and AMP²⁻ is identical; this result is confirmed because even

the 4-fold negatively charged ATP⁴⁻ fits into this picture (entries 1, 4, and 5 in Table 4), which is also in accord with the fact that the position of the PO₃²⁻ group at the ribose moiety has no effect: that is, the adduct stability of (Phen)(N)²⁻ for N = 2'-, 3'-, and 5'-AMP²⁻ is identical (entries 2–4).

Table 4. Stability constants, $K_{(Arm)(N)}^{(N)}$ (M^{-1}) (eq. (1)), for the formation of stacking adducts between 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) or 2,2-bipyridine (Bpy) and the nucleobase moieties of several nucleosides or nucleotides (N) in aqueous solution as determined by 1H -NMR shift or UV spectrophotometric measurements

No.	(Arm)(N)	$K_{(Arm)(N)}^{(N)}$ as determined by		Ref.
		1H -NMR ^a	UV ^b	
1	(Phen)(Ado)	42 ± 10		Table 3 (1)
2	(Phen)(2'-AMP) ²⁻	36 ± 11		100
3	(Phen)(3'-AMP) ²⁻	33 ± 8		100
4	(Phen)(5'-AMP) ²⁻	38 ± 6		100
5	(Phen)(ATP) ⁴⁻	38 ± 8		105
6	(Bpy)(Ado)		23 ± 4	75
7	(Bpy)(AMP) ²⁻		26 ± 6	75
8	(Bpy)(ATP) ⁴⁻	16 ± 4	8 ± 5	105/75
9	(Phen)(Ino)	49 ± 4		Table 3 (2)
10	(Phen)(IMP) ²⁻	49 ± 5		Table 3 (5)
11	(Bpy)(Ino)		20 ± 10	75
12	(Bpy)(IMP) ²⁻		14 ± 4	75
13	(Bpy)(ITP) ⁴⁻		28 ± 7	75
14	(Bpy)(Urd)	~2.4 ^c	3.2 ± 1.5	106
15	(Bpy)(UTP) ⁴⁻	~1.2 ^c		106
16	[Co(Bpy)](Ado) ²⁺		21 ± 7	76
17	[Ni(Bpy)](Ado) ²⁺		18 ± 8	76
18	[Cu(Bpy)](Ado) ²⁺		16 ± 10	76
19	[Co(Bpy)](Ino) ²⁺		23 ± 8	76
20	[Ni(Bpy)](Ino) ²⁺		12 ± 9	76
21	[Cu(Bpy)](Ino) ²⁺		21 ± 13	76

^a The 1H -NMR shift experiments were done in D₂O (25°C or 27°C; $I = 0.1 M$, NaNO₃). The $K_{(Arm)(N)cor}^{(N)}$ values are listed (see Table 3). The error limits correspond to twice the standard deviation (2σ).

^b These values were determined by UV-difference spectrophotometry in H₂O (25°C). The error limits for entries 6–8 and 11–13 are estimates; the measurements were made at the natural ionic strength, but a change in I had no remarkable effect on the stability constant⁷⁵. The error limits for entries 14–21 correspond to 3σ ($I = 0.1 M$, NaClO₄).

^c The values given in the literature¹⁰⁶ were corrected for the self-association of Bpy¹⁰⁵ by a factor of 1.2.

(ii) The observation described in (i) also holds if Phen is replaced by Bpy, i.e., if (Bpy)(N) stacks are considered, and this despite the scatter of the constants (see also (iii)). In this context it may be mentioned that the agreement between results obtained from 1H -NMR shift experiments and those from spectrophotometry is not al-

ways very satisfying; the reason is probably that the spectrophotometric measurements require very high concentrations which may hamper the experiments (transparency) and give also rise to self-association and high ionic strengths⁷⁷.

(iii) Based on the experience with the results given in Table 3, one expects that the stabilities of the Bpy adducts in entries 6–8 of Table 4, formed with the adenine residue (A), are the same; at first sight this does not seem to be the case, but if one calculates the average of these values, one obtains $K_{(Bpy)(A)av}^{(A)} = 18 \pm 8 M^{-1}$ (2σ), a value which overlaps within the error limits with those listed in Table 4 (entries 6–8).

(iv) However, despite all uncertainties, there is no doubt that the stability of the adducts formed with an adenine residue and Bpy is significantly lower than that formed with Phen. This is also borne out by a comparison of $K_{(Phen)(N)cor/av}^{(N)} = 44.4 \pm 3.8 M^{-1}$ (Section 3, point (v)) with the above value of $K_{(Bpy)(A)av}^{(A)} = 18 \pm 8 M^{-1}$. This result is easily understood because the aromatic rings of Bpy are considerably less suitable for an overlap with a purine moiety than is Phen (Fig. 2). The stability decrease amounts to a factor below one half.

(v) From entries 9–13 in Table 4 it is immediately obvious that the conclusion of point (iv) is fully confirmed by the hypoxanthine derivatives. The average for inosine and its nucleotides (I) (entries 11–13) leads to $K_{(Bpy)(I)av}^{(I)} = 21 \pm 8 M^{-1}$ (2σ), which is much below the values for (Phen)(I) (entries 9, 10: $49 \pm 5 M^{-1}$) but in accord with $K_{(Bpy)(A)av}^{(A)} = 18 \pm 8 M^{-1}$ (point (iv)).

(vi) Of high significance is the observation that the stability of the adducts formed between Bpy and the uracil residue (U) (entries 14, 15) is very low; i.e., $K_{(Bpy)(U)av}^{(U)} \sim 2.3$. This becomes especially evident if the constants for all Bpy/purine systems (P) are averaged (entries 6–8 and 11–13): $K_{(Bpy)(P)av}^{(P)} = 19.3 \pm 5.4 M^{-1}$ (2σ). Hence, the stability of uracil stacks is nearly by a factor of 1/10 lower. This is rationalized by the fact that pyrimidines offer for a stacking interaction only a single ring in contrast to purines which offer two; hence, pyrimidine derivatives are clearly disfavored for a stacking interaction

with a two-ring system like Bpy (or a larger one like Phen).

(vii) A final important point follows from a comparison of entries 16–18 and 19–21 in Table 4 with entries 6 and 9, respectively; these stability constants are identical within the error limits, meaning that coordination of a metal ion to Bpy does not significantly affect the stability of the stacks. If one generalizes these observations as well as the previous ones (point (i) above and Section 3, point (iii)), one may conclude that as long as one of the two partners, which form a stack, is uncharged, the stability of the stack is not affected in a significant manner if the other partner changes its charge, be it the heteroaromatic amine (Arm) or the nucleobase residue (Section 3, point (iii)) as well as the presence of a phosphate group (point (i)).

5. The cooperative effect of an additional ionic interaction on the stability of binary stacks

No doubt, the selective interactions between amino acid side chains and nucleobase residues are most important for the selectivity observed in biological systems. It is thus of interest to consider systems in which Phen or Bpy is replaced by an amino acid with side chains allowing interactions. Most suitable for a stacking interaction is of course the indole residue of tryptophan (Trp)⁷⁹; a weak hydrophobic interaction may be expected¹⁰⁷ with the isopropyl residue of leucine (Leu) (for the structures see Fig. 2).

Fortunately some relevant association constants have been determined via ¹H-NMR upfield shift measurements^{79–81,108}. The corresponding results are listed in Table 5; indeed, they allow several interesting conclusions:

(i) Comparison of entry 1 with 3 and entry 2 with 4 in Table 5 confirms the larger stability of stacks formed with purines compared to those with pyrimidines (see Section 4, point (vi)).

(ii) Comparison of entries 5 and 6 indicates, as one would expect, that the stacking tendency of the purine moiety is somewhat increased if a further ring is added. Indeed, ATP and ε-ATP differ by the formation of the 1,N⁶-etheno bridge which gives rise to a 5-membered ring.

(iii) Comparison of entries 3–5 with 7 and 8 shows that mere hydrophobic interactions as they occur with the

Table 5. Stability constants, $K_{(Aa)(N)}^{(N)}$ (M^{-1}) (analogous to eq. (1)), for the formation of stacking or hydrophobic adducts between the indole residue of tryptophan (Trp) or the isopropyl residue of leucine (Leu) and the nucleobase moieties of several nucleotides (N)^a

No.	(Aa)(N)	$K_{(Aa)(N)}^{(N)}$ (M^{-1})	Ref.
1	(Trp)(CMP) ³⁻	0.14 ± 0.10	80
2	[H(Trp)](CMP) ²⁻	0.77 ± 0.70	80
3	(Trp)(AMP) ³⁻	2.24 ± 0.58	80
4	[H(Trp)](AMP) ²⁻	6.83 ± 1.62	80
5	[H(Trp)](ATP) ⁴⁻	6.2 ± 1.2	79
6	[H(Trp)](ε-ATP) ⁴⁻	7.5 ± 0.8	81
7	(Leu)(ATP) ⁵⁻	0.4 ± 0.2 ^b	108
8	[H(Leu)](ATP) ⁴⁻	0.6 ± 0.3 ^b	108

^a The constants were determined by ¹H-NMR shift experiments in D₂O (27°C; *I* = 0.1 M, NaNO₃ or KNO₃). The range of error given is twice the standard deviation (2σ).

^b These constants and their error ranges are estimates based on ¹H-NMR shift experiments in H₂O (34°C; *I* = 0.1 to ca. 2 M, KNO₃).

isopropyl residue of leucine are considerably less stable than aromatic-ring stacking adducts.

(iv) The most important point, however, follows from comparisons of entries 1 with 2, 3 with 4, and 7 with 8 as well. The adducts formed with a nucleotide and a monoprotonated amino acid are in all instances considerably more stable than the corresponding adducts containing the amino acid anions. This observation can only mean that the protonated and positively charged amino group of the amino acids undergoes an ionic interaction with the negatively charged phosphate residue of the nucleotides and that this bridging enhances the stability of the adducts. This means that these ionic interactions, possibly including hydrogen bonds between the -NH₃⁺ and -PO₃²⁻ groups, give rise to synergistic effects.

(v) Finally, comparison of the values given for $K_{(Trp)(N)}^{(N)}$ in column 3 of Table 5 (entries 3–6) with the corresponding $K_{(Arm)(N)}^{(N)}$ values of Table 4 indicates that the indole moiety forms somewhat less stable stacks with nucleobases than Bpy and Phen.

6. A metal ion bridge favors the extent of a stacking interaction

6.1. Evaluation procedure regarding the stability of intramolecular stacks in mixed ligand complexes

In the preceding section we have seen that forming an ionic link between the two aromatic partners in the stack-

ing adduct enhances the stability of this adduct. Such a stability enhancement is also expected for metal ion bridging as is indicated in the intramolecular equilibrium (3) given in Section 1, where the metal ion is coordinated on the one hand to Arm (= Phen or Bpy) and on the other to the phosphate group of a nucleotide.

If we consider, e.g., complex formation between a metal ion (M^{2+}) already coordinated to Arm, that is, $M(\text{Arm})^{2+}$, and a nucleotide N and if we take the situation described by eq. (2) (see Section 1) into account, we obtain (neglecting charges) the following equilibrium (8a), the stability constant of which (eq. (8b)) is experimentally accessible, e.g., via potentiometric pH titrations^{55,73,100}:

$$K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)}^{M(\text{Arm})} = \frac{[M(\text{Arm})(N)]}{[M(\text{Arm})][N]} = \frac{([M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}] + [M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{st}}])}{[M(\text{Arm})][N]} \quad (8b)$$

In case the stacked species $M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{st}}$ does not form, equilibrium (8a) reduces to a simple complexation reaction and the corresponding stability constant of the open form is defined by eq. (9):

$$K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}}^{M(\text{Arm})} = [M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}]/([M(\text{Arm})][N]) \quad (9)$$

Evidently it has to be the aim to obtain values for the dimensionless equilibrium constant $K_{I/st}$, already defined by eq. (2b),

$$K_{I/st} = [M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{st}}]/[M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}] \quad (2b)$$

which describes the position of the intramolecular equilibrium (3) [which is analogous to eq. (2a)] (see Section 1). Since any additional interaction as it occurs, e.g., in the stacked $M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{st}}$ isomer, must be reflected in an enhanced complex stability compared to the open $M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}$ isomer, one may define a logarithmic stability difference between the measured stability constant [which encompasses all $M(\text{Arm})(N)$ species present (eq. (8b)) with the same analytical composition] and the one of the open isomer (eq. (10)):

$$\log \Delta_{M/\text{Arm}/N} = \log K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)}^{M(\text{Arm})} - \log K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}}^{M(\text{Arm})} = \log \Delta \quad (10)$$

Values for $K_{I/st}$ may be calculated^{107,109,110} with eq. (11):

$$K_{I/st} = \frac{K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)}^{M(\text{Arm})}}{K_{M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{op}}}^{M(\text{Arm})}} - 1 = 10^{\log \Delta} - 1 \quad (11)$$

Of course, once $K_{I/st}$ is known, also the percentage of the stacked isomer in the intramolecular equilibrium (3) may be calculated with eq. (12):

$$\% M(\text{Arm})(N)_{\text{st}} = 100 \cdot K_{I/st} / (1 + K_{I/st}) \quad (12)$$

Clearly, eq. (11) is applicable, provided the stability constant of the open isomer in equilibria (2a) and (3) can be quantified (eq. (9)). For ternary $M(\text{Arm})(\text{NMP})$ complexes this has been achieved via straight line correlations for $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ versus $pK_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ plots (eqs. (13), (14))¹¹¹⁻¹¹³, where R-PO_3^{2-} represents phosphate monoester or phosphonate ligands, in which the residue R is unable to interact with $\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})^{2+}$.

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Bpy})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Bpy})} = 0.465 \times pK_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}} + 0.009 \quad (13)$$

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Phen})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Phen})} = 0.465 \times pK_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}} + 0.018 \quad (14)$$

The error limits of log stability constants calculated with given $pK_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ values and eqs. (13) or (14) are ± 0.07 and ± 0.06 (3σ) log units¹¹¹⁻¹¹³, respectively, in the pK_a range 5–8.

Eqs. (13) and (14) are based on equilibrium constants determined for ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{R-PO}_3)$ complexes, where $\text{R-PO}_3^{2-} = \text{D-ribose 5-monophosphate, methanephosphonate and ethanephosphonate}$ ¹¹¹. On these $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ versus $pK_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ straight-line correlations also the data pairs measured for the corresponding methyl phosphate systems fit¹¹⁴. An example is given in Fig. 4, where the reference lines as defined by eqs. (13) and (14) are seen and where the stability constants $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{AMP})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ versus the acidity constant $pK_{\text{H}(\text{AMP})}^{\text{H}}$ are plotted¹⁰⁰ together with a related example¹¹⁵ that re-

fers to an acyclic AMP analogue, i.e., 9-(4-phosphonobutyl)adenine (dPMEA = 3'-deoxa-PMEA; see the third paragraph in Section 1) which is of interest in antiviral research^{49,73,116}: It has the formula adenineN(9)-CH₂CH₂CH₂CH₂-PO₃²⁻. Also for this compound the stability constant $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{dPMEA})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ versus the acidity constant $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{dPMEA})}^{\text{H}}$ is plotted in Fig. 4. The data points

Fig. 4. Evidence for an enhanced stability of the ternary Cu(Arm) (AMP) and Cu(Arm)(dPMEA) complexes (O, ●), where Arm = Bpy (O) or Phen (●), based on the relationship between $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ or $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{N})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ or $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{N})}^{\text{H}}$ in aqueous solution at $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO₃) and 25°C. The plotted data for AMP are from Ref. 100 and those for dPMEA from Ref. 115. The two reference lines represent the $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Arm})}$ versus $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ relationship for the ternary Cu(Arm)(R-PO₃) complexes (eqs. (13) and (14)); R-PO₃²⁻ symbolizes phosphonates or phosphate monoesters in which the group R is unable to undergo any kind of hydrophobic, stacking or other type of interaction, i.e., ligands like D-ribose 5-monophosphate, methanephosphonate or ethanephosphonate¹¹¹. The broken line holds for Arm = Bpy and the solid line for Arm = Phen. Both straight lines represent the situation for ternary complexes without an intramolecular ligand-ligand interaction. The vertical broken lines emphasize the stability differences from the reference lines; they equal $\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Arm}/\text{N}}$ as defined in eq. (10).

for the four ternary complexes, i.e., two each for Cu(Arm)(AMP)¹⁰⁰ and Cu(Arm)(dPMEA)¹¹⁵ are far above the reference lines, proving an increased complex stability which must mean that aside from the phosph(on)ate-Cu(Arm)²⁺ coordination further interactions occur and that equilibrium (3) exists.

The vertical differences in Fig. 4 between the data points for Cu(Arm)(AMP) and Cu(Arm)(dPMEA) and their reference lines correspond to $\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Arm}/\text{N}}$ as defined in eq. (10). Note, this corresponds to the fact that with $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{AMP})}^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{dPMEA})}^{\text{H}}$ and the straight-line eqs. (13) and (14) the stabilities of the open isomers (eq. (9)) can be calculated; they are represented in Fig. 4 by the intercepts of the vertical dotted lines with the reference lines. Application of the indicated procedure leads quite generally to $\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Arm}/\text{N}}$ values which quantify in an exact manner the enhanced stability of the ternary Cu(Arm)(N) complexes.

In fact, that for example for Cu(Phen)(dPMEA) an enhanced stability, i.e., a positive value for $\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Phen}/\text{dPMEA}}$ (see Fig. 4), is observed, proves that at least to some extent an intramolecular stacking interaction (eq. (3)) in this mixed ligand complex must occur. A tentative structure of such a stacked species is depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Tentative and simplified structure of a Cu(Phen)(dPMEA) species with an intramolecular stack. The orientation of the aromatic rings may vary among the stacked species; such a stacked complex in solution should not be considered as being rigid, hence, equilibria are expected between such stacks.

6.2. Stability comparisons for intramolecular stacks in ternary M(Phen)(N) and related complexes

From the stability enhancements seen in Fig. 4 it fol-

lows unequivocally that M(Phen)(N) and M(Bpy)(N) species may form intramolecular stacks as indicated in equilibrium (3). Therefore, we have summarized in Table 6 a significant part of the available stability data¹¹⁷⁻¹²¹ concentrating especially on adducts involving 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen).

Two points warrant initial emphasis: *Firstly*, from entries 1–3 in Table 6 it follows that the extent of intramolecular stack formation in the Cu(Phen)(N) species with N = AMP²⁻, ADP³⁻ and ATP⁴⁻ does not vary significantly, it remains close to 90%. This is interesting because the stability constants of the complexes (eq. (8)) in going from the AMP²⁻ to the ATP⁴⁻ species change by a factor of about 10³; i.e., $\log K_{\text{Cu(Phen)(AMP)}}^{\text{Cu(Phen)}} = 3.89 \pm 0.01$ (cf.¹⁰⁰), $\log K_{\text{Cu(Phen)(ADP)}}^{\text{Cu(Phen)}} = 6.52 \pm 0.04$ (cf.⁵⁷) and $\log K_{\text{Cu(Phen)(ATP)}}^{\text{Cu(Phen)}} = 6.88 \pm 0.07$ (cf.¹⁰⁵). *Secondly*, the stabilities of the binary (Phen)(AMP)²⁻ stacks for 2'-, 3'- and 5'-AMP are within the error limits identical, meaning that $K_{\text{(Phen)(AMP)}}^{\text{(AMP)}}$ is close to 36 M⁻¹ (see Section 4; Table 4); that is, the position of the phosphate group at the ribose ring has clearly no effect on the stability of the binary adducts; this also holds for the charge of the phosphate residue as the example with (Phen)(ATP)⁴⁻ demonstrates (Table 4, entry 5). However, in the mixed ligand complexes Cu(Phen)(AMP) the situation changes completely (Table 6; entries 1, 8 and 9): The extent of the intramolecular interaction decreases in the series 2'-AMP²⁻ > 5'-AMP²⁻ > 3'-AMP²⁻. In other words, metal ion coordination creates an individual behavior: % Cu(Phen)(AMP)_{st} increases from 56 ± 9% (log Δ = 0.36) for 3'-AMP²⁻ via 90 ± 2% (log Δ = 0.99) for 5'-AMP²⁻ to 97.2 ± 0.5% (log Δ = 1.56) for 2'-AMP²⁻. This clearly means that the steric restrictions are such that the most extensive overlap between the aromatic ring systems occurs with 2'-AMP²⁻. Also 5'-ATP⁴⁻ fits into this picture, it behaves in the ternary complex like 5'-AMP²⁻ having a formation degree of 91 ± 3% for the intramolecular stack (Table 6; entry 3).

Another point of interest linked to the above observations is the fact that the extent of intramolecular stacking in the Cu(Phen)(dPMEA) and Cu(Phen)(PMEA) complexes is within the error limits equal to that in Cu(Phen)(5'-AMP) (Table 6; entries 1, 10 and 11), being close to 90%. This observation confirms the earlier conclusion^{50,122,123} that the two acyclic nucleotide analogues

PMEA²⁻ and dPMEA²⁻ are "structure-wise" good mimics of 5'-AMP²⁻ and that this is of relevance for the antiviral activity of PMEA^{49,50,116,124}.

In the above context of considering formation degrees of stacks, the caveat mentioned in the terminating paragraph of Section 1 has to be recalled, namely that the equilibrium constants $K_{\text{(Arm)(N)}}^{\text{(N)}}$ (eq. (1)) and $K_{\text{I/st}}$ (eq. (2)) cannot directly be compared because the first constant has the dimension M⁻¹ whereas the second one is dimensionless. This problem has been recognized already more than 25 years ago¹⁰⁵, where it was demonstrated that in solutions with a reactant concentration of 10⁻³ M the binary (Phen)(ATP)⁴⁻ stack is present to about 3.5% (based on the total concentration) whereas the ternary Cu²⁺ complex forms at pH about 7 nearly completely, ca. 90% being stacked, which means that the Cu²⁺ bridge promotes the concentration of the stack by a factor of about 25.

Obviously, the results assembled in Table 6 allow many more interesting comparisons; a few are discussed below:

(i) That the extent of the possible aromatic-ring overlap is an important parameter in the determination of the stability of the intramolecular stacks is confirmed by the larger formation degree of the M(Phen)(N)_{st} species compared with that of the corresponding M(Bpy)(N)_{st} complexes (cf., e.g., entries 1–3 with 20–22) (see also Fig. 4).

(ii) A result analogous to (i) is seen if the stacking tendency in M(Phen)(5'-N) complexes is compared for those containing a purine moiety (e.g., entries 1, 2 and 3) with those containing a pyrimidine moiety (entries 7, 18 and 14): The two-ring purine residue forms more stable stacks than the single-ring pyrimidine residue. The difference for the complexes containing the adenine compared with the uracil residue amounts to a reduced stability enhancement of about 0.6 log units.

(iii) In the context of (ii) it is revealing to compare the Cu(Phen)(N) with the Cu(Bpy)(N) complexes for N = uracil derivative (cf. entries 7, 18 and 14 with 24, 32 and 28 in Table 6) and to note that the stability enhancement is throughout close to approximately 0.35 log units. This means, there is no significant difference in the formation degrees of the corresponding intramolecular stacks. This is understandable because for a single-ring uracil residue

Table 6. Extent of intramolecular stack formation in ternary M(Phen)(N) and some related M(Bpy)(N) complexes as calculated (eqs. (11) and (12)) from stability constants (eq. (8)) determined via potentiometric pH titrations: Stability enhancement $\log \Delta_{M/Arm/N}$ (eq. (10)), intramolecular and dimensionless equilibrium constant $K_{I/st}$ (eq. (11)) and percentage (eq. (12)) of the stacked $M(Arm)(N)_{st}$ species in aqueous solution (25°C; $I = 0.1$ M, $NaNO_3$)^a

No.	M(Arm)(N)	$\log \Delta_{M/Arm/N}$	$K_{I/st}$	% M(Arm)(N) _{st}	Ref.
1	Cu(Phen)(AMP)	0.99 ± 0.08	8.77 ± 1.81	90 ± 2	100
2	Cu(Phen)(ADP) ⁻	0.80 ± 0.08	5.31 ± 1.16	84 ± 3	57
3	Cu(Phen)(ATP) ²⁻	1.07 ± 0.15	10.7 ± 4.1	91 ± 3	10, 105 ^b
4	Mg(Phen)(ATP) ²⁻	~ 1.0	~ 9	~ 90 ^c	15 ^d
5	Ca(Phen)(ATP) ²⁻	~ 1.0	~ 9	~ 90	15 ^d
6	Zn(Phen)(ATP) ²⁻			(≥ 95) ^c	79
7	Cu(Phen)(UTP) ²⁻	0.46 ± 0.22	1.88 ± 1.46	65 ± 18	10, 105 ^b
	Cu(Phen)(2'-AMP)	1.56 ± 0.08	35.3 ± 6.7	97.2 ± 0.5	100
9	Cu(Phen)(3'-AMP)	0.36 ± 0.09	1.29 ± 0.45	56 ± 9	100
10 ^e	Cu(Phen)(dPMEA)	0.96 ± 0.12	8.12 ± 2.52	89 ± 3	115
11 ^f	Cu(Phen)(PMEA)			92 ± 2	111
12 ^g	Cu(Phen)(dGMP)	1.33 ± 0.10	20.38 ± 4.92	95.3 ± 1.1	55
13	Cu(Phen)(CMP)	0.42 ± 0.07	1.63 ± 0.44	62 ± 6	110
14	Cu(Phen)(UMP)	0.33 ± 0.07	1.14 ± 0.34	53 ± 7	110
15 ^h	Cu(Phen)(dTMP)	0.44 ± 0.06	1.75 ± 0.39	64 ± 5	110
16	Cu(Phen)(GDP) ⁻	1.30 ± 0.08	18.95 ± 3.68	95.0 ± 0.9	117
17	Cu(Phen)(CDP) ⁻	0.38 ± 0.11	1.40 ± 0.62	58 ± 11	118
18	Cu(Phen)(UDP) ⁻	0.29 ± 0.10	0.95 ± 0.46	49 ± 12	118
19 ^h	Cu(Phen)(dTDP) ⁻	0.30 ± 0.07	1.00 ± 0.32	50 ± 8	118
20	Cu(Bpy)(AMP)	0.73 ± 0.08	4.37 ± 1.02	81 ± 4	100
21	Cu(Bpy)(ADP) ⁻	0.70 ± 0.07	4.01 ± 0.81	80 ± 3	57
22	Cu(Bpy)(ATP) ²⁻	0.84 ± 0.15	5.92 ± 2.39	86 ± 5	10, 105 ^b
23	Zn(Bpy)(ATP) ²⁻	~ 0.54	~ 2.5	~ 70 ^c	119
24 ⁱ	Zn(Bpy)(UTP) ²⁻	~ 0.45	~ 1.8	~ 65 ^c	119
25	Cu(Bpy)(dPMEA)	0.78 ± 0.10	5.03 ± 1.39	83 ± 4	115
26 ^g	Cu(Bpy)(dGMP)	1.20 ± 0.09	14.85 ± 3.28	93.7 ± 1.3	55
27	Cu(Bpy)(CMP)	0.31 ± 0.08	1.04 ± 0.38	51 ± 9	110
28	Cu(Bpy)(UMP)	0.23 ± 0.07	0.70 ± 0.26	41 ± 9	110
29 ^h	Cu(Bpy)(dTMP)	0.35 ± 0.06	1.24 ± 0.30	55 ± 6	110
30	Cu(Bpy)(GDP) ⁻	1.12 ± 0.08	12.18 ± 2.43	92.4 ± 1.4	117
31	Cu(Bpy)(CDP) ⁻	0.40 ± 0.10	1.51 ± 0.60	60 ± 9	118
32	Cu(Bpy)(UDP) ⁻	0.36 ± 0.10	1.29 ± 0.54	56 ± 10	118
33 ^h	Cu(Bpy)(dTDP) ⁻	0.35 ± 0.08	1.24 ± 0.40	55 ± 8	118

^a The error limits are three times the standard error of the mean value or the sum of the probable systematic error, whichever is larger; the error propagation was calculated after Gauss.

^b These values are taken from Table 8 in Ref. 10; they are based on data presented in Ref. 105. The error limits are in part (oversized) estimates, calculated with the information provided in Ref. 105. In addition, the listed data are in a systematic way also rather lower limits (for details see Ref. 105).

^c ¹H-NMR shift experiments⁷⁹ in D₂O (27°C; $I = 0.1$ M, $NaNO_3$) gave the following results: % Mg(Phen)(ATP)_{st}²⁻ = ca. 100%; % Zn(Phen)(ATP)_{st}²⁻ ≥ 95%; % Zn(Bpy)(ATP)²⁻ = 55%; % Zn(Bpy)(UTP)²⁻ = ca. 40%.

^d The data given in Ref. 15 are based on spectrophotometric experiments presented in Ref. 77 (25°C; $I = 0.1$ M, $NaClO_4$). The results from potentiometric pH titrations are similar⁷⁷.

^e See Figs. 4 and 5.

- ^f PMEA = 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine = adenineN(9)-CH₂CH₂-O-CH₂-PO₃²⁻; for details see Ref. 111. The evaluation is complicated by the fact that also about 6 (±2)% 5-membered chelated complex species form which involve the ether oxygen of the aliphatic chain. Only about 1.8 (±0.3)% of the species are solely phosphate-coordinated.
- ^g dGMP²⁻ = 2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-monophosphate (see Fig. 1). The data are based on the log Δ values given in the second column of Table 4 in Ref. 55. For Cu(Phen)(dGMP)_{cl/N7} and Cu(Bpy)(dGMP)_{cl/N7} the formation degrees of the macrochelates were estimated⁵⁵ as being 6 ± 7% and 8 ± 9%. In other words, at best traces of macrochelates occur in the ternary Cu(Arm)(dGMP) complexes.
- ^h dTMP²⁻ = thymidine 5'-monophosphate = 1-(2'-deoxy-β-D-ribofuranosyl)thymine 5'-monophosphate; thymine = 5-methyluracil (see Fig. 1). For dTDP³⁻ the corresponding description is valid.
- ⁱ For Cu(Bpy)(UTP)²⁻ the same result is obtained within the error limits despite the different coordination geometries of Cu²⁺ (Ref. 120) and Zn²⁺ (Ref. 121): log Δ_{Cu/Bpy/UTP} = 0.45 ± 0.22. $K_{1/st}$ = 1.82 ± 1.43, % Cu(Bpy)(UTP)_{st}²⁻ = 65 ± 18% (see Table 8 in Ref 10)^b.

a single-ring partner is enough and therefore Phen offers no significant advantage over Bpy (Fig. 2).

(iv) Another conclusion of general importance is possible from a comparison of the stability enhancements (log Δ; eq. (10)) observed for the Cu(Phen)(NMP) (Table 6; entries 14, 12, 15, 1 and 12), Cu(Phen)(NDP)⁻ (entries 18, 17, 19, 2 and 16) and Cu(Bpy)(NMP) (entries 28, 27, 29, 21 and 26) series. The only variable within a given type of complex is the nucleobase. Hence, overall the following trend for an increasing stacking property of the nucleobase moieties is obtained: uracil ≤ cytosine ~ thymine < adenine < guanine (Fig. 1). The formation degree of the intramolecular stack in Cu(Arm)(OMP)⁻, where OMP³⁻ = orotidinate 5'-monophosphate, exists¹²⁵, is similar to the one observed for Cu(Arm)(UMP) (entries 14 and 28). The Cu(Arm)(XMP - H)⁻ species, where (XMP - H)³⁻ = xanthosinate 5'-monophosphate, shows a formation degree of the intramolecular stack which is a bit less pronounced^{126,127} than the one in Cu(Arm)(5'-AMP) (entries 1 and 20) possibly because of the negative charge present in the nucleobase residue¹²⁶⁻¹²⁸ which leads to a redistribution of the electron densities.

(v) The ternary M(Phen)(ATP)²⁻ complexes (Table 6; entries 3-6) show a formation degree for the intramolecular stack of approximately 90%, independent of the metal ion, i.e., be it Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺ or Zn²⁺. This observation is very interesting as it shows that these species are so flexible that the aromatic rings can stack well independent of the steric restrictions imposed by the different coordination geometries of the four metal ions. The formation degrees of the stacks in the corresponding Cu(Phen)(UTP)²⁻ (entry 7) and M(Bpy)(ATP)²⁻ complexes (entries 22 and 23) are smaller than expected, confirming once again that the size of the ring systems affects the

stability of the stacking adducts.

(vi) There is one further point that warrants emphasis: The stability of the binary (Bpy)(UTP)⁴⁻ stack is very low ($K_{(Bpy)(UTP)}^{(UTP)}$ = ca. 1.2 M⁻¹; Table 4; entry 15) and could hardly be determined^{79,106}. However, the formation degree of about 65% for the intramolecular stacks in Cu(Phen)(UTP)²⁻ (entry 7) and Cu(Bpy)(UTP)²⁻ or Zn(Bpy)(UTP)²⁻ (entry 24) is quite considerable. This example emphasizes an important point: A metal ion is able to facilitate the recognition between two moieties by linking them together into the same species!

6.3. Stacking and hydrophobic interactions involving nucleotides and amino acids

With the results discussed in Section 5 (Table 5) in mind, one expects that in M(ATP)(Trp)³⁻ complexes intramolecular stacks (analogous to Fig. 6) are formed and that consequently equilibria analogous to eqs. (2a) and (3) occur. The results assembled in Table 7 confirm this expectation.

Of course, the percentages given in Table 7 for M(N)(Aa)_{st}, where N represents a nucleotide and Aa an amino acid anion, i.e., either tryptophanate or leucinate, are in many instances only rough estimates as the stability differences log Δ_{M/N/Aa} (cf., eq. (10)) are small, but still, together with the results from the ¹H-NMR shift experiments also indicated in Table 7, they prove that intramolecular adducts analogous to equilibrium (3) are formed and they allow the following conclusions:

(i) Entries 1-4 in Table 7 show that in the M(ATP)(Trp)³⁻ complexes the formation degree of the intramolecular stack with an average of about 50% is quite pronounced. This should be compared with the extent of the hydrophobic adduct formation (see Fig. 6) in

Table 7. Intramolecular aromatic-ring stacking or hydrophobic adduct formation, both types of interactions being denoted here as "stacks", in ternary M(N)(Aa) complexes, where N = nucleotide and Aa = amino acid anion, in analogy to equilibrium (3) (see also Fig. 6) and as calculated (analogously to eq. (8)) from stability constants determined via potentiometric pH titrations: The extent of the interactions is quantified by the stability enhancement $\log \Delta_{M/N/Aa}$ (analogously to eq. (10)), the intramolecular and dimensionless equilibrium constant $K_{I/st}$ (eq. (11)) and the percentage of the "stacked" species (eq. (12)) in aqueous solution (25°C; $I = 0.1$ M, NaClO₄ or KNO₃)^a

No.	M(N)(Aa)	$\log \Delta_{M/N/Aa}$	$K_{I/st}$	% M(N)(Aa) _{st}	Ref.
1	Mg(ATP)(Trp) ³⁻			44 ± 19 ^b	81
2	Mn(ATP)(Trp) ³⁻	0.32 ± 0.11	1.09 ± 0.52	52 ± 12	108
3	Cu(ATP)(Trp) ³⁻	0.19 ± 0.09	0.55 ± 0.33	35 ± 14	108
4	Zn(ATP)(Trp) ³⁻	0.59 ± 0.06	2.89 ± 0.51	73 ± 3 ^b	108
5	Mn(ATP)(Leu) ³⁻	0.23 ± 0.22	0.70 (0.023/1.82) ^c	41 (2.3/65) ^c	108
6	Cu(ATP)(Leu) ³⁻	0.10 ± 0.08	0.26 (0.047/0.51) ^c	21 (4.5/34) ^c	108
7	Zn(ATP)(Leu) ³⁻	0.02 ± 0.09	0.05 (~0/0.29) ^c	5 (~0/22) ^{c,d}	108
8	Cd(ATP)(Leu) ³⁻			10 (5/25) ^{c,d}	108
9	Pb(ATP)(Leu) ³⁻			25 (15/70) ^{c,d}	108
10	Ni(AMP)(Trp) ⁻	0.37 ± 0.24	1.34 ± 1.30	57 ± 24	80
11	Ni(CMP)(Trp) ⁻	0.05 ± 0.13	0.12 (~0/0.51)	11 (~0/34)	80
12 ^e	Zn(ATP)(Im) ²⁻			~35 (15/50)	83

^a For the error limits see footnote *a* of Table 6. The error limits were (previously) calculated (see Table 6 in Ref. 10) based on the data given in Refs. 80 and 108.

^b From ¹H-NMR shift experiments in D₂O (27°C; $I = 0.1$ M, NaNO₃)⁸¹. For Zn(ATP)(Trp)_{st}³⁻ (entry 4) 40 ± 15% were found by this method⁸¹.

^c The values in parentheses give the lower and upper limits, respectively.

^d From ¹H-NMR shift experiments in H₂O (34°C; $I = 0.1$ – 1.5 M, KNO₃)¹⁰⁸. For Zn(ATP)(Leu)_{st}³⁻ (entry 7)^c 30 (20/75)% were found by this method¹⁰⁸.

^e Im = imidazole. For Cd(ATP)(Im)_{st}²⁻ within the error limits the same formation degree was obtained. From ¹H-NMR shift experiments in D₂O (27°C; $I = 0.1$ M, NaNO₃)⁸³.

the M(ATP)(Leu)³⁻ complexes (entries 5–9), which amounts on average to approximately 20–25%. Hence, this compares well with the observations made in connec-

Fig. 6. Tentative and simplified structure of the ternary complex formed by M²⁺, ATP⁴⁻ and Leu⁻, showing within the M(ATP)(Leu)³⁻ complex the interaction of the isopropyl group of Leu⁻ with the aromatic purine moiety of ATP⁴⁻. Replacement of the isopropyl group by the indole residue indicates then the stack formed in M(ATP)(Trp)³⁻ species.

tion with Table 5 in Section 5 and demonstrates again that a metal ion bridge can make a recognition significant, in this case between the isopropyl residue of leucinate and the purine moiety of ATP⁴⁻.

(ii) Entries 10 and 11 for Ni(AMP)(Trp)⁻ and Ni(CMP)(Trp)⁻ confirm, despite the large error limits, the previous conclusion (Section 6.2) that the purine moiety is better suited for stack formation than the pyrimidine moiety. This is important regarding recognition reactions of nucleotides and nucleic acids.

(iii) In the present context it may also be mentioned that the evaluation of ¹H-NMR shift experiments⁸³ led to the conclusion that in aqueous solution the Zn(ATP)(Im)²⁻ and Cd(ATP)(Im)²⁻ complexes form an intramolecular stack (entry 12) between the adenine residue and imidazole (= Im) with a formation degree between about 15–50%. This result agrees with the suggestion¹²⁹, based on thermodynamic parameters, that in Zn(ATP)(histamine)²⁻ stacking occurs. In addition, very recently a formation

degree of the intramolecular stack in Cu(UTP)(histamine)²⁻ was estimated as being $55 \pm 15\%$ ¹³⁰. Considering that here a one-ring–one-ring interaction takes place, this value agrees well with the other systems considered here.

(iv) The results in (iii), together with the one obtained for M(ATP)(Ala)³⁻ species, that by ¹H-NMR measurements no indication for an interaction between the methyl group of alaninate (Ala⁻) and the purine residue of ATP could be found¹⁰⁸, allow the following conclusion: The recognition of the adenine residue by the amino acid side chain in M(ATP)(Aa)³⁻ complexes decreases in the series tryptophan (indole residue) > histidine (imidazole residue) > leucine (isopropyl residue) > alanine (methyl group). We are convinced that this series of selectivity also holds for other cases in which amino acids/proteins interact with nucleotides/nucleic acids.

7. The effect of a decreasing solvent polarity on the stability of stacks

There is good evidence that the "equivalent solution" or "effective" dielectric constant (permittivity) is reduced in enzyme cavities¹³¹ or in certain locations in proteins^{132,133} as well as in ribozymes³³. The influence of a changing solvent polarity on complex equilibria is well-known^{9,27,131,134}. With these facts in mind, we assembled the information about the effect of 1,4-dioxane on the stability of binary stacks (Table 8) as well as on the stability of intramolecular stacks formed in ternary complexes (Table 9)^{27,135}.

Table 8. Stability constants, $K_{(Arm)(N)}^{(N)}$ (eq. (1)), for the formation of aromatic-ring stacking adducts between 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridine and ATP⁴⁻ in dependence on the amount of 1,4-dioxane added to an aqueous solution^a

No.	System	Solvent (v/v)	$K_{(Arm)(N)}^{(N)}$
1	(Phen)(ATP) ⁴⁻	D ₂ O	38 ± 8
2	(Phen)(ATP) ⁴⁻	30% D ₆ -diox./D ₂ O	4.8 ± 1.1
3	(Phen)(ATP) ⁴⁻	50% D ₆ -diox./D ₂ O	1.8 ± 0.7
4	(Bpy)(ATP) ⁴⁻	D ₂ O	16 ± 4
5	(Bpy)(ATP) ⁴⁻	30% D ₆ -diox./D ₂ O	3.5 ± 2
6	(Bpy)(ATP) ⁴⁻	50% D ₆ -diox./D ₂ O	0.4 ± 0.2
7 ^b	(Bpy)(UTP) ⁴⁻	D ₂ O	~ 1.2

^a The constants were determined by ¹H-NMR shift experiments in deuterated solvents (27°C; *I* = 0.1 M, NaNO₃)¹⁰⁵. The error limits correspond to twice the standard deviation (2σ).

^b The stability of this adduct is given for comparison; it is taken from entry 15 in Table 4.

In Table 8 the effect of 1,4-dioxane on the formation constants of intramolecular stacks according to equilibrium (1a) is summarized. All of these simple unbridged stacks are dramatically destabilized already by small amounts of organic solvents. It should be noted that in an aqueous solution containing 30% (v/v) of 1,4-dioxane its mole fraction is only 0.083 (and the dielectric constant $\epsilon = 52.7$)^{27,135}. This amount is evidently enough to strongly solvate via hydrophobic interactions of the ethylene units of dioxane the individual aromatic rings and in this way to shift equilibrium (1a) for (Arm)(ATP)⁴⁻ to the left.

The above results (Table 8) should be compared with those given in Table 9 where the effect of 1,4-dioxane on the stability of the stacks in Cu(Arm)(NTP)²⁻ and Cu(Arm)(GDP)⁻ is seen^{105,117}. Despite the in part rather large error limits, it is clear that even in 50% 1,4-dioxane the formation degree of the intramolecular stacks is still quite remarkable.

From the data in Table 9 it is apparent that equilibrium (3) involving the formation of intramolecular, i.e., metal ion-bridged, stacks between the aromatic rings of 1,10-phenanthroline (entries 1–3) or 2,2'-bipyridine (entries 4–6) and the nucleobase moieties of ATP (and also UTP; entries 7–12) is affected by 1,4-dioxane, but by far not as much as the binary stacks formed between Phen or Bpy and ATP⁴⁻. By going from an aqueous solution to 50% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane-water the stability of the unbridged (Phen)(ATP)⁴⁻ or (Bpy)(ATP)⁴⁻ adducts decreases by factors of about 1/20 or more (Table 8; entries 1, 3 and 4, 6), while the metal-bridged ternary adducts are disfavored only by factors of about 1/2 (Table 9; entries 1, 3 and 4, 6). In other words, the concentration of the stacked isomer of the ternary complexes is quite large even in 50% aqueous dioxane. The same applies for the Cu(Arm)(GDP)⁻ species (entries 13–18). However, in this connection one should also point out that there are special cases known^{9,19,27,134}, where the addition of 1,4-dioxane or ethanol to an aqueous solution even promotes the formation of intramolecular stacks or hydrophobic adducts in ternary Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ complexes, probably due to solvation of these adducts by the organic solvent molecules. Clearly, this contrasts with any experience regarding binary adducts (see also Table 8).

Table 9. Extent of intramolecular stack formation in ternary Cu(Arm)(N) complexes (N = ATP⁴⁻, UTP⁴⁻ or GDP³⁻) as calculated from stability constants (eq. (8)) determined via potentiometric pH titrations: Stability enhancement $\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Arm}/\text{N}}$ (eq. (10)), intramolecular and dimensionless equilibrium constant $K_{\text{I/st}}$ (eq. (11)), and percentage (eq. (12)) of the stacked Cu(Arm)(N)_{st} species in aqueous solution as well as in water containing 30% (v/v) or 50% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane (25°C; I = 0.1 M, NaNO₃)^{a,b}

No.	Cu(Arm)(N)	% (v/v) 1,4-diox.	$\log \Delta_{\text{Cu}/\text{Arm}/\text{N}}$	$K_{\text{I/st}}$	% Cu(Arm)(N) _s
1 ^c	Cu(Phen)(ATP) ²⁻	0	1.07 ± 0.15	10.7 ± 4.1	91 ± 3
2 ^c		30	0.41 ± 0.15	1.57 ± 0.89	61 ± 13
3 ^c		50	0.29 ± 0.15	0.95 ± 0.67	49 ± 18
4	Cu(Bpy)(ATP) ²⁻	0	0.84 ± 0.15	5.92 ± 2.39	86 ± 5
5		30	0.30 ± 0.15	1.00 ± 0.69	50 ± 17
6		50	0.21 ± 0.15	0.62 ± 0.56	38 ± 21
7	Cu(Phen)(UTP) ²⁻	0	0.46 ± 0.22	1.88 ± 1.46	65 ± 18
8		30	0.10 ± 0.18	0.26 (~0/0.91) ^d	21 (~0/48) ^d
9		50	0.17 ± 0.19	0.48 (~0/1.29) ^d	32 (~0/56) ^d
10	Cu(Bpy)(UTP) ²⁻	0	0.45 ± 0.22	1.82 ± 1.43	65 ± 18
11		30	0.12 ± 0.13	0.32 (~0/0.78) ^d	24 (~0/44) ^d
12		50	0.11 ± 0.11	0.29 (~0/0.66) ^d	22 (~0/40) ^d
13	Cu(Phen)(GDP) ⁻	0	1.30 ± 0.08	18.95 ± 3.68	95.0 ± 0.9
14		30	0.08 ± 0.09	0.20 (~0/0.48) ^d	17 (~0/32) ^d
15		50	0.12 ± 0.13	0.32 (~0/0.78) ^d	24 (~0/44) ^d
16	Cu(Bpy)(GDP) ⁻	0	1.12 ± 0.08	12.18 ± 2.43	92.4 ± 1.4
17		30	0.25 ± 0.09	0.78 ± 0.36	44 ± 12
18		50	0.25 ± 0.12	0.78 ± 0.49	44 ± 16

^a For the error limits see footnote *a* of Table 6.

^b The results in entries 1–12 are summarized from data presented in Ref. 105 (see also Table 8 in Ref. 10). The error limits are in part (oversized) estimates which have been calculated with the information provided in Ref. 105. In addition, the data listed above are in a systematic way also rather lower limits (for details, see Ref. 105). – Entries 13–18 are from Ref. 117.

^c The mol fractions of 1,4-dioxane for entries 1, 2, and 3 are 0, 0.083 and 0.175, and the permittivities (dielectric constants, ϵ)^{27,135} 78.5, 52.7, and 35.2, respectively. This holds analogously also for entries 4–18.

^d The values in parentheses are the lower and upper limits, respectively.

To further illustrate the point that the formation of a metal ion bridge between the individual parts of a stacking adduct^{27,136} favors the stability of this adduct dramatically let us compare the percentage of the stacked adduct present in 10⁻³ M solutions¹⁰⁵ of the reactants for the Phen/ATP⁴⁻ and Cu²⁺/Phen/ATP⁴⁻ systems. For an aqueous solution we have already seen that the formation of the metal ion bridge leads to a promotional factor of approximately 25 (see the fourth paragraph in Section 6.2). Even more dramatic is the situation in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water¹⁰⁵. Here exist in the binary Phen/ATP system only about 0.18% of the reactants in the stacked (Phen)(ATP)⁴⁻ form, whereas in the ternary system, where the complex at pH about 7 is formed to more than 90%, the stacked isomer is still present with about 46%, i.e., the promotion factor amounts now to more than 250.

Such effects definitely influence selectivity in biological systems.

8. Conclusions and outlook

In this account we have considered the formation of binary stacks formed between the "indicator" ligand Phen and purine nucleosides or nucleotides (N) (Section 3). Surprisingly, the formation and stability of these adducts is rather independent of the purine derivative considered, and also of its charge. For example, deprotonation of the (N1)H site in guanosine does not affect the stability of the (Phen)(Guo) adduct remarkably. Similarly, the position of the phosphate group at the ribose ring does not affect adduct stability as is evident from (Phen)(AMP)²⁻ adducts, where AMP²⁻ = 2', 3'- or 5'-AMP²⁻. In addition, 5'-ATP also fits into this picture (Section 4). This indif-

ference is relatively surprising and in contrast to the self-association of all these species (Section 2), where the kind of nucleobase considered and also the charge have a significant effect.

However, the indicated "indifference" in the stability of binary stacks disappears as soon as bridging occurs, be it via an ionic interaction like in [H(Trp)](ATP)⁴⁻ (Section 5) or via a metal ion bridge like in the M(Arm)(ATP)²⁻ species, where Arm = Phen or Bpy (Section 6). For example, the extents of stacking in the Cu(Phen)(AMP) complexes with AMP²⁻ = 2'-, 3'- or 5'-AMP²⁻ differ now strongly; under the influence of a metal ion these AMPs suddenly become "individuals". Furthermore, the quantification of intramolecular stack formation in mixed ligand complexes allowed the conclusion (Section 6.2) that the tendency of nucleobases to form stacks increases in the series uracil \lesssim cytosine \sim thymine $<$ adenine $<$ guanine. However, here more work is needed because the order Ade $<$ Gua apparently depends on the systems considered¹⁰, and also the hypoxanthine residue needs to be placed. Similarly, regarding the affinity of amino acid side chains and the recognition by the adenine moiety of ATP⁴⁻ in ternary complexes, the following series is obtained: indole residue (Trp) $>$ imidazole group (histidine) $>$ isopropyl residue (Leu) $>$ methyl group (Ala) (Section 6.3). Again, more work is needed: Other M(N)(Aa) combinations need to be studied and the phenyl and phenol residues of phenylalanine and tyrosine, respectively, need to be included. Finally, it should be emphasized that the extents of stacking and hydrophobic interactions are playing a role in the recognition between two species as is evident from the low-molecular-weight examples discussed in this account.

This view is supported, e.g. by the described "hydrophobic" interaction¹³⁷ which occurs between three tyrosine residues (of the pol α RB69 DNA polymerase) and DNA to form a tight fitting binding pocket at the minor groove site. Similarly, for T7 RNA polymerase it was shown¹³⁸ that during translocation a tyrosine residue stacks with nucleobases of DNA and RNA. A related example emphasizes further the general importance of stacking interactions, that is, in *Anabaena* flavodoxin the isoalloxazine moiety of flavin mononucleotide (FMN) is sandwiched by the aromatic rings of hydroxyphenyl (tyrosine) and indole (tryptophan) residues¹³⁹.

Finally, it should be emphasized that the energy differences, which are connected with adduct formation as exemplified by equilibria (2a) and (3) are very small. For example, the energy difference (ΔG^0) that is involved with the transformation of 20% of the open form into the closed or stacked form, corresponds only^{66,109,113} to -0.6 kJ mol^{-1} at 25°C, which means that the stability of the corresponding mixed ligand complex increases by 0.1 log unit ($= \log \Delta$; cf., eq. (10)). These are subtle changes that allow Nature to shift easily the connected equilibria in either direction, but still, the selectivity is large if, e.g., only the stacked isomer is a suitable substrate for an enzymic reaction.

9. Experimental

9.1. Materials

Adenosine and 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate (pro analysi) were purchased from Merck AG (Darmstadt, FRG). Guanosine and guanosine 5'-monophosphate were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA), and inosine and inosine 5'-monophosphate were from Serva Feinbiochemica GmbH (Heidelberg, FRG). All the other reagents were the same as used previously^{59,100}.

9.2. Measurements

The ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian VXR 400 spectrometer (399.96 MHz) at 25°C in D₂O using the center peak of the triplet signal of the tetramethylammonium ion (2.5 mM) as internal standard. However, all measured chemical shifts were converted to the (sodium) 3-(trimethylsilyl)propane-1-sulfonate reference by adding to the internal standard^{60,105} 3.174 ppm (see also Ref. 96). To avoid signal broadening due to paramagnetic impurities, the measured solutions contained some EDTA (5% based on [N])⁹⁹. The NMR spectra were recorded immediately after preparation of the solutions. The desired pH of each solution was adjusted by dotting with a relatively concentrated DNO₃ or NaOD on a thin glass rod⁴¹, and it was measured with a Metrohm pH meter⁵⁹ before and after recording the NMR spectrum. These two direct pH meter readings^{59,60} were averaged, and the corresponding values of a given series (Fig. 3; see also below) were averaged again and a value of 0.40 was added¹⁴⁰ to this mean value to get the pH of the series⁶⁰.

The selection procedure for the desired pD of a series (Table 3) is described in Section 3.1.

The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ signals of the nucleosides and nucleotides were assigned as given previously⁴¹⁻⁴³. The concentration of the nucleosides or nucleotides was always 5 mM and the concentration range of 1,10-phenanthroline varied from 0 to $[\text{Phen}]_{\text{max}}$ as given in parentheses after the pD of a series: Ado at pD 7.53 (0.019 M), Ino at pD 7.44 (0.019 M) (Fig. 3), Guo at pD 7.63 (0.018 M), IMP^{2-} at pD 8.20 (0.018 M), GMP^{2-} at pD 8.39 (0.017 M), $(\text{Ino} - \text{D})^-$ at pD 11.15 (0.017 M), $(\text{Guo} - \text{D})^-$ at pD 11.27 (0.018 M), $(\text{IMP} - \text{D})^{3-}$ at pD 11.26 (0.017 M), and $(\text{GMP} - \text{D})^{3-}$ at pD 11.29 (0.017 M). The given upper concentration of Phen is close to the solubility limit of this compound.

The stability constants of the binary (Phen)(N) adducts (see Table 3) formed between Phen and the nucleosides or nucleotides at the various pD values were determined by plotting the measured upfield shifts of H2, H8 and H1' of the adenosine and inosine systems, and of H8 and H1' of the guanosine systems in dependence on the increasing concentration of Phen (see Fig. 3 as an example). The experiments and their evaluation were carried out as described^{100,105}. The series with IMP^{2-} at pD 8.20 and $(\text{Ino} - \text{D})^-$ at pD 11.15 were measured twice; all the other ones were done once.

Acknowledgments

The recording of the 400-MHz NMR spectra by Mrs. Karin Ulrich, technician of the NMR-service laboratory of the Institute of Organic Chemistry, and the support of our work by the Department of Chemistry of the University of Basel are gratefully acknowledged.

References

- O. Takahashi, Y. Kohno and M. Nishio, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 6049-6076.
- S. Grimme, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 3430-3434.
- M. Nishio, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 6923-6950.
- O. Yamauchi, A. Odani and M. Takani, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 3411-3421.
- (a) J.-M. Lehn, "Supramolecular Chemistry. Concepts and Perspectives", VCH, Weinheim, 1995; (b) E. C. Constable, C. E. Housecroft, M. Mayor, W. P. Meier, C. G. Palivan, H. A. Wegner and H. Wennemers, *Chimia*, 2010, **64**, 877-884.
- E. A. Meyer, R. K. Castellano and F. Diederich, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 1210-1250.
- S. Y. Brauchli, E. C. Constable, K. Harris, D. Häussinger, C. E. Housecroft, P. J. Rösel and J. A. Zampese, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 10739-10748.
- (a) K. Müller-Dethlefs and P. Hobza, *Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **100**, 143-167; (b) K. S. Kim, P. Tarakeshwar and J. Y. Lee, *Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **100**, 4145-4185.
- H. Sigel, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1989, **61**, 923-932.
- O. Yamauchi, A. Odani, H. Masuda and H. Sigel, *Met. Ions Biol. Syst.*, 1996, **32**, 207-270.
- (a) C. Meiser, B. Song, E. Freisinger, M. Peilert, H. Sigel and B. Lippert, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**, 388-398; (b) E. Freisinger, R. Griesser, B. Lippert, C. F. Moreno-Luque, J. Niclós-Gutiérrez, J. Ochocki, B. P. Operschall and H. Sigel, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2008, **14**, 10036-10046.
- (a) H. B. Gray and J. R. Winkler, *Quart. Rev. Biophysics*, 2003, **36**, 341-372; (b) J. C. Lee, J. E. Kim, E. V. Pletneva, J. Faraone-Mennella, H. B. Gray and J. R. Winkler, *Met. Ions Life Sci.*, 2006, **1**, 9-60.
- (a) E. C. Constable, C. E. Housecroft, M. Creus, K. Gademann, B. Giese, T. R. Ward, W.-D. Woggon and A. Chougnet, *Chimia*, 2010, **64**, 846-854; (b) M. Cordes and B. Giese, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 892-901.
- F. M. Al-Sogair, B. P. Operschall, A. Sigel, H. Sigel, J. Schnabl and R. K. O. Sigel, *Chem. Rev.*, 2011, **111**, in press. DOI: 10.1021/cr100415s.
- H. Sigel in "Coordination Chemistry - 20", ed. D. Banerjee, Published by IUPAC through Pergamon Press, Oxford and New York, 1980, pp. 27-45.
- R. Tribolet, H. Sigel and K. Trefzer, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **79**, 278-280.
- T. Yajima, G. Maccarrone, M. Takani, A. Contino, G. Arena, R. Takamido, M. Hanaki, Y. Funahashi, A. Odani and O. Yamauchi, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2003, **9**, 3341-3352.
- H. Sigel, R. Tribolet and K. H. Scheller, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **100**, 151-164.
- G. Liang, R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 2877-2887.
- G. Liang, R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **155**, 273-280.
- (a) J. Kyte, *Biophys. Chem.*, 2003, **100**, 193-203; (b) L. Wu, D. McElheny, T. Takekiyo and T. A. Keiderling, *Biochemistry*, 2010, **49**, 4705-4714.
- L. W. Tari, A. Matte, H. Goldie and L. T. J. Delbaere, *Nat. Struct. Biol.*, 1997, **4**, 990-994.
- (a) R. K. O. Sigel, E. Freisinger and B. Lippert, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 219-220; (b) R. K. O. Sigel, M. Sabat, E. Freisinger, A. Mower and B. Lippert, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 1481-1490; (c) R. K. O.

- Sigel, E. Freisinger and B. Lippert, *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, **5**, 287-299.
24. O. Kühn, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 1235-1246.
 25. (a) R. K. O. Sigel, S. M. Thompson, E. Freisinger, F. Glahe and B. Lippert, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2001, **7**, 1968-1980; (b) R. K. O. Sigel, E. Freisinger, M. Abbate and B. Lippert, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **339**, 355-365; (c) R. K. O. Sigel, S. M. Thompson, E. Freisinger and B. Lippert, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, 19-20.
 26. K. H. Scheller, T. H. J. Abel, P. E. Polanyi, P. K. Wenk, B. E. Fischer and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1980, **107**, 455-466.
 27. H. Sigel, R. Malini-Balakrishnan and U. K. Häring, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 5137-5148.
 28. H. Sigel, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1998, **70**, 969-976.
 29. (a) L.-n. Ji and X. Le, *Chinese Sci. Bull.*, 2002, **47**, 1-9; (b) T. Yajima, R. Takamido, Y. Shimazaki, A. Odani, Y. Nakabayashi and O. Yamauchi, *Dalton Trans.*, 2007, 299-307.
 30. (a) C. F. Naumann, B. Prijs and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1974, **41**, 209-216; (b) H. Sigel, P. Waldmeier and B. Prijs, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Letters*, 1971, **7**, 161-169.
 31. W. Saenger, "Principles of Nucleic Acid Structure", Springer Verlag, New York, 1984.
 32. "Interplay between Metal Ions and Nucleic Acids", Vol. 10 of *Metal Ions in Life Sciences*, eds. A. Sigel, H. Sigel and R. K. O. Sigel, Springer Sci. & Business Media, Dordrecht (The Netherlands), 2012, in press.
 33. R. K. O. Sigel and A. M. Pyle, *Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **107**, 97-113.
 34. M. C. Erat, O. Zerbe, T. Fox and R. K. O. Sigel, *ChemBioChem*, 2007, **8**, 306-314.
 35. "Structural and Catalytic Roles of Metal Ions in RNA", Vol. 9 of *Metal Ions in Life Sciences*, eds. A. Sigel, H. Sigel and R. K. O. Sigel, The Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge (U.K.), 2011.
 36. C. M. Yang and J. Zhang, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 10854-10865.
 37. "Electron Transfer Reactions in Metalloproteins", Vol. 27 of *Metal Ions in Biological Systems*, eds. H. Sigel and A. Sigel, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1991.
 38. J. D. Slinker, N. B. Muren, S. E. Renfrew and J. K. Barton, *Nature Chem.*, 2011, **3**, 230-235.
 39. K. Kawai, H. Kodera, Y. Osakada and T. Majima, *Nature Chem.*, 2009, **1**, 156-159.
 40. J. C. Genereux and J. K. Barton, *Nature Chem.*, 2009, **1**, 106-107.
 41. K. H. Scheller, F. Hofstetter, P. R. Mitchell, B. Prijs and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 247-260.
 42. K. H. Scheller and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 5891-5900.
 43. N. A. Corfù, R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1990, **191**, 721-735.
 44. N. A. Corfù and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1991, **199**, 659-669.
 45. S. Yanagisawa, K. Sato, M. Kikuchi, T. Kohzuma and C. Dennison, *Biochemistry*, 2003, **42**, 6853-6862.
 46. T. Skauge, I. Turel and E. Sletten, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **339**, 239-247.
 47. N. G. A. Abrescia, L. Malinina and J. A. Subirana, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1999, **294**, 657-666.
 48. (a) H. Sigel, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **100**, 453-539; (b) H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **198-200**, 1-11.
 49. (a) H. Sigel, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2004, **33**, 191-200; (b) H. Sigel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 261-271.
 50. H. Sigel, C. A. Blindauer, A. Holý and H. Dvořáková, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 1219-1220.
 51. C. Bazzicalupi, A. Bencini, E. Berni, A. Bianchi, P. Fornasari, C. Giorgi, C. Marinelli and B. Valtancoli, *Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 2564-2572.
 52. C. Bazzicalupi, A. Bencini, A. Bianchi, A. Danesi, C. Giorgi, C. Lodeiro, F. Pina, S. Santarelli and B. Valtancoli, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 2630-2632.
 53. Y. Guo, Q. Ge, H. Lin, H. K. Lin, S. Zhu and C. Zhou, *Biophys. Chem.*, 2003, **105**, 119-131.
 54. M. Chikira, Y. Tomizawa, D. Fukita, T. Sugizaki, N. Sugawara, T. Yamazaki, A. Sasano, H. Shindo, M. Palaniandavar and W. E. Antholine, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2002, **89**, 163-173.
 55. M. S. Lüth, L. E. Kapinos, B. Song, B. Lippert and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 357-365.
 56. M. S. Lüth, B. Song, B. Lippert and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, **39**, 1305-1310.
 57. E. M. Bianchi, S. A. A. Sajadi, B. Song and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2000, **300-302**, 487-498.
 58. J. Talib, D. G. Harman, C. T. Dillon, J. Aldrich-Wright, J. L. Beck and S. F. Ralph, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 504-513.
 59. R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1987, **163**, 353-363.
 60. R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1987, **27**, 119-130.
 61. H. Sigel and N. A. Corfù, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1996, **240**, 508-517.
 62. R. B. Martin and Y. H. Mariam, *Met. Ions Biol. Syst.*, 1979, **8**, 57-124.
 63. D. B. Davies, P. Rajani and H. Sadikot, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 279-285.
 64. K. Aoki, *Met. Ions Biol. Syst.*, 1996, **32**, 91-134.
 65. H. Sigel, *Biol. Trace Element Res.*, 1989, **21**, 49-59.

66. H. Sigel, *ACS Symp. Series*, 1989, **402**, 159-204.
67. H. Sigel, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2004, **76**, 375-388.
68. H. Sigel and R. Griesser, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2005, **34**, 875-900.
69. L.-n. Ji, N. A. Corfù and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 1367-1375.
70. K. H. Scheller and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1986, **157**, 147-153.
71. H. Sigel, *Chimia*, 1987, **41**, 11-26.
72. M. Bastian and H. Sigel, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1997, **67**, 27-34.
73. A. Fernández-Botello, A. Holý, V. Moreno, B. P. Operschall and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **362**, 799-810.
74. A. Fernández-Botello, A. Holý, V. Moreno and H. Sigel, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2004, **98**, 2114-2124.
75. C. F. Naumann and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 2750-2756.
76. P. Chaudhuri and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 3142-3150.
77. P. R. Mitchell and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 1564-1570.
78. C. F. Naumann and H. Sigel, *FEBS Lett.*, 1974, **47**, 122-124.
79. P. R. Mitchell, B. Prijs and H. Sigel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **62**, 1723-1735.
80. J. B. Orenberg, B. E. Fischer and H. Sigel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 785-792.
81. H. Sigel, K. H. Scheller, V. Scheller-Krattiger and B. Prijs, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 4171-4178.
82. A. I. Anzellotti, C. A. Bayse and N. P. Farrell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 10425-10431.
83. H. Sigel, R. Tribolet and O. Yamauchi, *Comments Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **9**, 305-330.
84. H. Irving and D. H. Mellor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 5222-5237.
85. G. Anderegg, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **46**, 2397-2410.
86. (a) H. Sigel and A. Sigel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 501-509; (b) A. Sigel and H. Sigel, *Chemical Monthly (Monatsh. Chem.)* [Preface for "Metals in the Brain"], 2011, **142**, 323-324.
87. "Handbook on Metalloproteins", eds. I. Bertini, A. Sigel and H. Sigel, Marcel Dekker, New York, 2001.
88. "Neurodegenerative Diseases and Metal Ions", Vol. 1 of *Metal Ions in Life Sciences*, eds. A. Sigel, H. Sigel and R. K. O. Sigel, Wiley, Chichester (U.K.), 2006.
89. H. R. Lucas and K. D. Karlin, *Met. Ions Life Sci.*, 2009, **6**, 295-361.
90. P. O. P. Ts'o, I. S. Melvin and A. C. Olson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1289-1296.
91. P. R. Mitchell and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1978, **88**, 149-154.
92. M. P. Schweizer, A. D. Broom, P. O. P. Ts'o and D. P. Hollis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1042-1055.
93. K. J. Neurohr and H. H. Mantsch, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 1986-1994.
94. (a) R. Bretz, A. Lustig and G. Schwarz, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1974, **1**, 237-241; (b) H. Sapper and W. Lohmann, *Biophys. Struct. Mech.*, 1978, **4**, 327-335; (c) D. M. Cheng, L. S. Kan, P. O. P. Ts'o, C. Giessner-Prettre and B. Pullman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 525-534.
95. T.-D. Son and C. Chachaty, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1973, **335**, 1-13.
96. F. E. Evans and R. H. Sarma, *Biopolymers*, 1974, **13**, 2117-2132.
97. (a) J.-L. Dimicoli and C. Hélène, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 1036-1044; (b) M. P. Heyn and R. Bretz, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1975, **3**, 35-45.
98. R. B. Martin, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 3043-3064.
99. R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1988, **170**, 617-626.
100. S. S. Massoud, R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1990, **187**, 387-393.
101. H. Sigel, S. S. Massoud and R. Tribolet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 6857-6865.
102. H. Sigel, S. S. Massoud and N. A. Corfù, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 2958-2971.
103. G. Kampf, L. E. Kapinos, R. Griesser, B. Lippert and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 2002, 1320-1327.
104. R. B. Martin, *Science*, 1963, **139**, 1198-1203.
105. R. Tribolet, R. Malini-Balakrishnan and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1985, 2291-2303.
106. Y. Fukuda, P. R. Mitchell and H. Sigel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **61**, 638-647.
107. B. E. Fischer and H. Sigel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 2998-3008.
108. H. Sigel, B. E. Fischer and E. Farkas, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 925-934.
109. R. B. Martin and H. Sigel, *Comments Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **6**, 285-314.
110. S. S. Massoud and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **159**, 243-252.
111. D. Chen, M. Bastian, F. Gregáň, A. Holý and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1537-1546.
112. H. Sigel, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **144**, 287-319.
113. H. Sigel and L. E. Kapinos, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **200-202**, 563-594.
114. J. Zhao, B. Song, N. Saha, A. Saha, F. Gregáň, M.

- Bastian and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1996, **250**, 185-188.
115. R. B. Gómez-Coca, L. E. Kapinos, A. Holý, R. A. Vilaplana, F. González-Vílchez and H. Sigel, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001, **84**, 39-46.
116. A. Holý, *Curr. Pharm. Design*, 2003, **9**, 2567-2592.
117. B. P. Operschall, E. M. Bianchi, R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 23-39.
118. S. A. A. Sajadi, B. Song and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **283**, 193-201.
119. H. Sigel, K. H. Scheller and R. M. Milburn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1933-1938.
120. H. Sigel and R. B. Martin, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 385-426.
121. H. Sigel and R. B. Martin, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1994, **23**, 83-91.
122. C. H. Schwalbe, W. Thomson and S. Freeman, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1991, 1348-1349.
123. C. A. Blindauer, A. Holý, H. Dvořáková and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1997, 2353-2363.
124. H. Sigel, B. Song, C. A. Blindauer, L. E. Kapinos, F. Gregáň and N. Prónayová, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, 743-744.
125. M. Bastian and H. Sigel, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1991, **23**, 137-154.
126. H. Sigel, B. P. Operschall, S. S. Massoud, B. Song and R. Griesser, *Dalton Trans.*, 2006, 5521-5529.
127. H. Sigel, B. P. Operschall and R. Griesser, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 2465-2494.
128. (a) S. S. Massoud, N. A. Corfù, R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2004, **10**, 5129-5137; (b) H. Sigel, S. S. Massoud, B. Song, R. Griesser, B. Knobloch and B. P. Operschall, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2006, **12**, 8106-8122.
129. G. Arena, R. Cali, V. Cucinotta, S. Musumeci, E. Rizzarelli and S. Sammartano, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1651-1658.
130. B. Knobloch, A. Mucha, B. P. Operschall, H. Sigel, M. Jeřowska-Bojczuk, H. Kozłowski and R. K. O. Sigel, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2011, **17**, 5393-5403.
131. H. Sigel, R. B. Martin, R. Tribolet, U. K. Häring and R. Malini-Balakrishnan, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1985, **152**, 187-193; see also the footnote on p. 258 in M. Bastian and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **178**, 249-259.
132. D. C. Rees, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1980, **141**, 323-326.
133. N. K. Rogers, G. R. Moore and M. J. E. Sternberg, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1985, **182**, 613-616.
134. G. Liang and H. Sigel, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1989, **44b**, 1555-1566.
135. (a) G. Åkerlöf and O. A. Short, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1241-1243; (b) G. Åkerlöf and O. A. Short, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6357; (c) F. E. Critchfield, J. A. Gibson, Jr. and J. L. Hall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1991-1992.
136. R. Malini-Balakrishnan, K. H. Scheller, U. K. Häring, R. Tribolet and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 2067-2076.
137. E. Freisinger, A. P. Grollman, H. Miller and C. Kisker, *EMBO J.*, 2004, **23**, 1494-1505.
138. Y. W. Yin and T. A. Steitz, *Cell*, 2004, **116**, 393-404.
139. S. T. Rao, F. Shaffie, C. Yu, K. A. Satyshur, B. J. Stockman, J. L. Markley and M. Sundaralingam, *Protein Sci.*, 1992, **1**, 1413-1427.
140. P. K. Glasoe and F. A. Long, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 188-190.

